

2nd TwINSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation
with Cutting-Edge Technologies

Book of Proceedings

University of Novi Sad
Faculty of Technology Novi Sad
Novi Sad, Serbia

6 - 7 June 2024

BOOK OF PROCEEDINGS

2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop

Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies

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Dear colleagues, participants of the 2nd TwiNSol-CECs Workshop,

On behalf of the TwiNSol-CECs team, I am delighted to welcome you all to our 2nd Workshop with title "Advanced Water Treatments in Emerging Contaminants Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies" organized in the frame of TwiNSol-CECs project (GA 101059867). We deeply appreciate your contributions in the form of oral and poster presentations, with the abstracts and full papers compiled in the Book of Abstracts and Proceedings, available on our project website (www.twinsol-cecs.com). We are really proud in securing this project under Horizon Europe patronage and are honored by the opportunities such as this event, enabled through execution of TwiNSol-CECs, to share knowledge and exchange ideas within the environmental research with colleagues from Serbia, Western Balkans, and EU.

This event aims to bring together scientists and experts focused on, but not limited to, the issues on removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water by innovative technologies. Since „Cutting-Edge Technologies” in water treatment are part of our focus in TwinSol-CECs project, the 2nd Workshop highlights three key innovative technologies: membrane processes, advanced oxidation, and biosorption. Each of these technologies offers unique and effective approach for removing micropollutants and contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water. These innovative technologies, each with its distinct advantages, represent significant advancements in our quest for clean and safe water. By integrating these methods, we can develop more comprehensive and effective strategies for managing water quality and protecting public health.

Beyond these topics, the Workshop also acts as a forum for exchanging research ideas, exploration of complementarities and possibilities for collaboration, contributing to the harmonization of research and innovation efforts crucial for the sustainable transition envisioned by the Horizon Europe and Green Deal calls towards a zero-pollution, toxic-free environment.

The TwiNSol-CECs team wishes you a pleasant stay in Novi Sad and looks forward to engaging discussions on new research ideas and collaborative efforts towards a zero-pollution future,

Prof. Zita Šereš
Chair

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Mitigation with Cutting-Edge Technologies*

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TWINNING FOR EXCELLENCE IN
ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES PROTECTION

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

PROGRAM OF THE 2nd TwiNSol-CECs WORKSHOP

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University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Serbia
 June 6-7, 2024

Thursday – 6 June 2024

Morning session, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Blue Hall
 (Chairs: Vanessa J. Pereira and Zita Šereš)

- 9:00 – 10:00 Registration (Entrance Hall of TFNS)
- 10:00 – 10:15 Official opening, Biljana Pajin, Dean of the Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, and Zita Šereš, Chair of the Workshop
- Plenary lectures (30 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):*
- 10:15 – 10:50 João G. Crespo, Sylwin Pawlowski, Svetlozar Velizarov – **Ion-Exchange Membrane Processes: Perspectives in Water Treatment and Desalination**
- 10:50 – 11:25 Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares – **Catalytic advanced oxidation processes for pollutants degradation**
- 11:25 – 11:55 *Coffee break*
- Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):*
- 11:55 – 12:15 Sanja Panić, Mirjana Petronijević, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Heteroatom-doped pyrochar for efficient metal-free catalytic oxidation of contaminants of emerging concern**
- 12:15 – 12:35 Minja M. Bogunović, Ivana I. Ivančev-Tumbas – **Hybrid adsorption/membrane filtration in water treatment for the removal of organic micropollutants**
- 12:35 – 12:55 Nandor Nemestothy, Merve Visnyei, Veronika Kalauz-Simon, Peter Bakonyi – **Gaseous Byproducts in Wastewater Treatment: Challenges and Opportunities with Membrane Technology**
- 13:00 – 14:00 *Lunch*
- 14:00 – 14:30 *Poster session with Coffee*

Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall

(Chairs: Nandor Nemestothy and Nikola Maravić)

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:30 – 14:50 Snežana Maletić, Jelena Beljin, Irina Jevrosimov, Tamara Apostolović, Srđan Rončević, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski – **The contribution of inoculated biochar to pesticide adsorption and biosorption**
- 14:50 – 15:10 Djordja V. Kerkez, Milena R. Bečelić-Tomin, Anita S. Leovac Mačerak, Dragana D. Tomašević Pilipović, Dejan Krčmar, Nataša S. Slijepčević, Vesna Z. Pešić – **Sludge application on land: Opportunities and challenge**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 15:10 – 15:25 Szabolcs Kertész, Imre Vajk Fazekas, Martin Trancsik, Aws N. Al-Tayawi, József Richárd Lennert, Sándor Beszédes, József Csanádi, Tamás Szabó, Cecilia Hodúr, Gábor Veréb, Zsuzsanna László – **Enhancing the efficiency of low-pressure membrane separations using 3d printed spacers**
- 15:25 – 15:40 Aws N. Al-Tayawi, Hajnalka Csott, Nikolett Sz. Gulyás, József Richárd Lennert, Zsuzsanna Horváth Hovorka, Zsuzsanna László, Cecilia Hodúr, Szabolcs Kertész – **Evaluation of flow dynamics utilizing integrated 3d printed turbulence promoters for mitigation of membrane fouling**
- 15:40 – 15:55 Jelena Molnar Jazić, Tajana Simetić, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Aleksandra Tubić, Jasmina Agbaba – **Advanced oxidation processes for natural organic matter and emerging contaminants abatement in water treatment**
- 15:55 – 16:10 Jasmina Nikić, Malcolm A. Watson, Maja Vujić, Jovana Pešić, Jovana Jokić-Govedarica, Srđan Rončević, Jasmina Agbaba – **Addressing arsenic contamination: a polymer-based nanocomposite for water treatment**

Friday – 7 June 2024

Morning session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall

(Chairs: João G. Crespo and Szabolcs Kertész)

- 9:00 – 10:00 Registration (Entrance Hall of TFNS)

Plenary lectures (30 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 10:00 – 10:30 Maria B. Cristóvão, Jorge Bernardo, Andreia Bento-Silva, Maria R. Bronze, João G. Crespo, Vanessa J. Pereira – **Mitigating Anticancer Drug Pollution: Nanofiltration for Control of Emerging Contaminants in Wastewater Effluents**

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 10:30 – 10:50 Nikola Maravić, Zita Šereš, Jelena Šurlan, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Carla Brazinha, Claudia F. Galinha, João G. Crespo – **Removal of acetaminophen and clarithromycin from water samples using nanofiltration and reverse osmosis**
- 10:50 – 11:10 Vesna M. Vasić, Dragana V. Lukić, Marina B. Šćiban – **Sewage sludge biochar as a sorbent for contaminants of emerging concerns removal from water**
- 11:10 – 11:30 Gábor Veréb, Laura Fekete, Tímea Miklós, Kata Fejes, Renáta Kovács, Ákos F. Fazekas, Erika Nascimben Santos, Szabolcs Kertész, Sándor Beszédes, Cecilia Hodúr, Zoltán Jákói, Gábor Kovács, Zsolt Pap, Tamás Gyulavári, Klára Hernádi, Zsuzsanna László – **TiO₂/CNT-modified pvdf composite membranes for enhanced membrane filtration of oily wastewaters**
- 11:30 – 12:00 *Coffee break*
- 12:00 – 12:20 Dragana, V. Lukić, Vesna, M. Vasić, Marina, B. Šćiban – **Multicomponent adsorption kinetics of micropollutants onto lignocellulosic biosorbents**
- 12:20 – 12:40 Nenad R. Grba – **Nano-geopolymer based remediation techniques for purification of different type of groundwater with high Mn, Fe and other metals/metalloids (As) content**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 12:40 – 12:55 Zoltán P. Jákói, Cecilia Hodúr, Sándor Beszédes – **Dielectric monitoring in wastewater-treatment and sludge utilization processes**
- 12:55 – 13:10 Maja Vujić, Vasiljević Sanja, Tajana Simetić, Jelena Molnar Jazić, Marijana Kragulj Isakovski, Jasmina Agbaba, Aleksandra Tubić – **Adsorption kinetitics of organic pollutants on microplastic fibers in water**
- 13:10 – 14:10 *Lunch with coffee*

Afternoon session, Faculty of Technology Blue Hall

(Chairs: Olívia Salomé G. P. Soares and Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović)

Invited lectures (15 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:10 – 14:30 Ferenc E. Kiss – **Lessons learnt from life cycle assessment of advanced wastewater treatment processes**
- 14:30 – 14:50 Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Role of a high-resolution mass spectrometry in investigating processes for removal of contaminants of emerging concern from water**

Oral presentations (10 min per lecture + 5 min for Q&A after each lecture):

- 14:50 – 15:05 Marija Šobić, Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Milan Tomić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović – **Removal of micropollutants from water using hydrochar obtained with process water recirculation**

- 15:05 – 15:20 Arijit Nath, Geremew Geidare Kailo, Abraham Amankwaa, Gabriella Kiskó, András Koris –
Production of Bioactive (Antioxidant and Antibacterial) Peptides from Soybean Milk Proteins by an Enzymatic Membrane Reactor
- 15:20 – 15:40 Concluding remarks

Poster presentations, Central Lobby of TFNS (set-up: June 6, 11:25 – 11:55, dismantling: June 7, 13:10 – 15:40)

- P1** APPLICATION OF PHYSICALLY ACTIVATED BIOCHAR FOR THE REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER
Aleksandra Adamović, Mirjana Petronijević, Saša Savić, Sanja Panić, Sanja Petrović, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P2** POTENTIAL OF HYDROCHAR AS BIOSORBENT FOR HEAVY METAL IONS REMOVAL FROM WATER
Marco Barbanera, Alessandro Cardarelli, Vesna M. Vasić, Dragana V. Lukić
- P3** INFLUENCE OF SELECTED CARRIER MATERIALS ON NATURAL COAGULANT PRODUCTION YIELD
Sanja Cojbasic, Maja Turk Sekulic, Jelena Prodanovic
- P4** APPLICATION OF LEDs IN UV/CHLORINE AOPs FOR THE TREATMENT OF AQUEOUS SOLUTIONS OF POPs SUCH AS PHARMACEUTICALS
Anett Čović, Luca Farkas, Constance Csaplár, Teodóra Dragić, Tünde Alapi
- P5** PREDICTION THE PHOTOCATALYTIC DEGRADATION RATE OF DICLOFENAC BY ARTIFICIAL NEURAL NETWORKS
 S. Roy, L. Das Samanta
- P6** ACTIVATION OF PEROXYMONOSULFATE WITH BIOCHAR - ADSORPTION AND ELIMINATION OF TRIMETHOPRIM ANTIBIOTIC FROM WATERS
Dinesh Chandola, Erik Sinkovics, Zsuzsanna László, Tünde Alapi
- P7** COMBINED ION EXCHANGE AND MICROFILTRATION
 Marijana Dragosavac
- P8** LIGNIN DERIVED FROM CYNARA CARDUNCULUS AS AN EFFICIENT BIOSORBENT FOR CHROMIUM(VI) ION REMOVAL FROM WATER
Jorge Gominho, Ana Lourenço, Ricardo A. Costa, Duarte M. Neiva, Vesna M. Vasić, Dragana V. Lukić, Marina B. Šćiban
- P9** JUTE FABRIC WASTE AS A PROMISING ADSORBENT FOR HEAVY METAL IONS AND ORGANIC DYES: A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW
 Aleksandra M. Ivanovska
- P10** REMOVAL OF PHENOL FROM WATER BY USING FREE AND IMMOBILIZED HORSE RADISH PEROXIDASE CATALYZED PROCESS
Milan P. Nikolić, Slobodanka Stanojević-Nikolić
- P11** PRODUCTION OF ANTIOXIDANT AND ANTIBACTERIAL PEPTIDES FROM SOYBEAN MEAL BY AN ENZYMATICAL MEMBRANE REACTOR
Arijit Nath, Geremew Geidare Kailo, Abraham Amankwaa, Gabriella Kiskó, András Koris

- P12** APPLICATION OF LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOSORBENT FOR SUGAR JUICE PURIFICATION IN FIXED-BED COLUMN
Lidija E. Perović, Jelena A. Miljanić, Julija Šupljika, Ivan Zdjelarević, Nikola R. Maravić, Zita I. Šereš
- P13** REMOVAL OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM WATER USING UV-H₂O₂ ADVANCED OXIDATION PROCESS
Mirjana Petronijević, Sanja Panić, Jelena Živančev, Igor Antić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
- P14** Cu²⁺ ADSORPTION FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION BY WASTE EGGSHELL POWDER
Sanja Petrović, Saša Savić, Mirjana Petronijević, Bratislav Todorović, Staniša Stojilković
- P15** PHENOL REMOVAL FROM WATER SOLUTION USING PEROXIDASE EXTRACTED FROM POTATO PEEL
Saša Savić, Sanja Petrović, Mirjana Petronijević
- P16** THE MICROPLASTIC IS VISIBLE BY FLUORESCENCE UNDER STEREOMICROSCOPE
 Živa Kolenc, Kaja Adamek, Sonja Smole Možina, Anja Klančnik
- P17** THE ADVANTAGE OF LPM LAMPS EMITTING AT 185 NM - A SIMPLE SOLUTION TO ENHANCE THE EFFICIENCY OF PHOTOCHEMICAL WATER POST-TREATMENT PROCESS FOR ELIMINATING NON-BIODEGRADABLE ORGANIC POLLUTANTS
Tünde Alapi, Anett Čović, Luca Farkas, Réka Bíró, Gyöngyi Orosz
- P18** INACTIVE BIOMASS OF THE FUNGUS *Ganoderma applanatum* AND ITS BIOSORPTIVE POTENTIAL FOR REMOVING MALACHITE GREEN FROM WASTEWATER
Natalija Velić, Marija Stjepanović, Jelena Vukoje, Janez Gorenšek, Sandra Budžaki, Marta Ostojčić
- P19** EFFECT OF SODIUM CHLORIDE ON THE REMOVAL OF PHARMACEUTICALLY ACTIVE COMPOUNDS FROM WATER BY A REVERSE OSMOSIS MEMBRANE
Jelena Šurlan, Zita Šereš, Nikola Maravić, Nataša Đurišić Mladenović, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev, Carla Brazinha, João G. Crespo
- P20** PRELIMINARY PRODUCTION COST ESTIMATION FOR BIOSORBENTS DERIVED FROM PEACH STONES
Danijela Z. Stefanović, Marija R. Miladinović, Biljana S. Đorđević, Milan D. Kostić, Olivera S. Stamenković
- P21** ADSORPTION EFFICIENCIES OF INDIAN NEEM LEAVES FOR REMOVAL OF CONGO-RED DYE FROM AQUEOUS SOLUTION FOR SUSTAINABLE ENVIRONMENT
Radharani Das, Ishita Sinha, Soumyajit Maity, Subhojit Ash
- P22** ADSORPTIVE REMOVAL OF Cr (VI) FROM SYNTHETIC WASTES USING AGRICULTURAL WASTES: A GREEN APPROACH
Radharani Das, G. Roymahapatra, Ishita Sinha, Soumyajit Maity, Subhojit Ash

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University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad,
Novi Sad, Serbia, 6-7 June 2024

PROCEEDINGS

HETEROATOM-DOPED PYROCHAR FOR EFFICIENT METAL-FREE CATALYTIC OXIDATION OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN

Sanja Panić*, ***Mirjana Petronijević***, ***Igor Antić***, ***Jelena Živančev***, ***Maja Buljovčić***, ***Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović***
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia,
**sanjar@tf.uns.ac.rs*

Abstract

In this study, novel metal-free carbocatalysts were prepared *via* simple green synthetic route (ball-milling and subsequent pyrolysis at 600°C) using pinewood sawdust, as pyrochar precursor, and cheap precursors of urea and boric acid as nitrogen and boron sources, respectively. The obtained single-doped (N-, B-doped), as well as the N,B-codoped pyrochar were employed as metal-free activators of peroxydisulfate for the degradation of 22 contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) in a water solution model mixture (10 µg/l concentration of each compound) – 11 pesticides and 11 pharmaceutically active compounds (PhACs). The role of dopants in synthesized catalysts was correlated with their performance in persulfate oxidation of selected CECs. Additionally, the degradation kinetics of each individual pollutant in a mixture has been explored. The results demonstrated that all the prepared carbocatalysts manifested excellent activity for 20 tested CECs, being superior activators for the degradation of pharmaceutically active compounds compared to the tested pesticides. The B-doped pyrochar exhibited great capability to boost persulfate activation for ~100% removal of 7 pesticides and all pharmaceutically active compounds. It is expected that this study provides new insights into the rational design of cost-effective, eco-friendly and highly efficient metal-free carbocatalysts as promising candidates for practical applications in the CECs removal from wastewater.

Keywords: Persulfate-based oxidation, Pyrochar, Metal-free carbocatalysts, CECs

Introduction

The widespread occurrence of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) has been a very important issue in the field of environmental remediation, giving rise to concerns about their potential toxic effects to aquatic ecosystems and human beings. Many of these compounds are not the subject of routine monitoring or emission control, and current efforts to prevent and mitigate their risks are insufficient (Feng et al., 2023). Due to a trace concentration, almost continuous emission, and often recalcitrant nature of various CECs detected in wastewater, conventional water treatment technologies are not efficient in their elimination. Additionally, the cost/energy-consuming aspect of the above-mentioned traditional technologies has initiated a considerable research effort to be dedicated to the development of advanced oxidation processes (AOPs) (Hu et al., 2019). Compared to other remediation methods, these processes offer several benefits including being eco-friendly, cost effective and possibility of achieving total mineralization of contaminants. Recently, persulfate-based AOPs (PS-AOPs) have emerged as an effective strategy for the abatement of emerging pollutants and a promising alternative to commonly used hydrogen-peroxide (H₂O₂). In general, these processes are based on the generation of reactive species, sulfate radicals - SO₄^{•-}, hydroxyl radicals - •OH, singlet oxygen - ¹O₂ and superoxide anion radicals - O₂^{•-}, with high potential abilities to degrade various CECs (Zaeni et al., 2020). Peroxymonosulfate (PMS) and peroxydisulfate (PDS) represent the initial compounds used for the production of these reactive species *via* diverse activation approaches (UV irradiation, heat, catalyst), and the activation mechanism can proceed by radical or nonradical pathways (Ghanbari and

Moradi, 2017). The application of heterogeneous catalysts for persulfate activation is simpler, more efficient and economical compared to energy-based activation methods. Two types of heterogeneous catalysts have been widely employed for PS activation – transition metal- and carbon-based ones. Although PS activation induced by various transition metal catalysts based on Fe, Co, Mn, and Cu has demonstrated excellent degradation efficiency for many organic contaminants, these catalysts suffer from excessive metal leaching, which may induce secondary pollution of the treated water (Oh et al., 2016). As an alternative strategy to replace metal-based PS catalysts, metal-free catalysts based on various types of carbonaceous materials have been proposed as ideal materials for PS activation due to their high surface area, porous structure, abundant functional groups, structural defects, great thermal stability, eco-friendliness, and overall, the possibility of tuning their electronic and physicochemical properties (Dean et al., 2018). In PS activation driven by metal-free carbocatalysts, the non-radical degradation pathways (singlet oxygen and electron transfer) are the dominant ones, emphasizing the beneficial aspects of these catalysts over the metal based-ones (Anfar et al., 2021). Namely, without the radicals being involved in the degradation mechanism, the performance of the process is rarely affected by several parameters related to the real water matrix - pH, presence of inorganic anions, and dissolved organic matters (Liu et al., 2021). Furthermore, in non-radical-based system the catalyst is not oxidized over repetitive use and its developed porous structure facilitates the adsorption of compounds on catalytic centers promoting the subsequent oxidation (Ye et al., 2023). Due to chemical inertness of pristine carbon materials, a strategy for boosting their catalytic performances relies on engineering the carbon structure by introducing foreign atoms - heteroatoms (e.g. N, B, S, P, Se) into the carbon lattice in order to modulate its surface properties and create more catalytic active centers (Wang and Chen, 2022). Besides being effective as PS activators, these modified carbocatalysts have to fulfil the long-term durability test and show low environmental toxicity. Within the scope of sustainability requirements, the production of heteroatom-doped carbocatalysts by means of simple and scalable method using cost-effective precursors is highly desirable. In terms of environmental remediation, biomass can be regarded as a prominent platform material for the preparation of pyrochar-based catalysts due to its renewable nature and natural abundance (Liu et al., 2015). Pyrochar, as biomass-derived carbon with easily-adjustable properties, has already shown great potential for wastewater treatment and still represents the hotspot of research in the field of environmental catalysis.

In the present study, single-doped (N-, B-doped), as well as the N,B-codoped pyrochar-based catalysts were successfully produced by one-step pyrolysis process involving *in situ* N and B functionalization. Pinewood sawdust was used as carbon precursor, while cheap precursors of urea and boric acid served as nitrogen and boron sources, respectively. The performances of the prepared carbocatalysts as PS activators were tested for the degradation of 22 CECs – 11 pesticides and 11 PhACs, as model contaminants. The main goal of this research is to design well effective and green persulfate-based catalytic system with high potential to be used in practical wastewater remediation facilities.

Materials and methods

Preparation of metal-free carbocatalysts

Pinewood sawdust, used as a precursor of pyrochar, was rinsed, dried and smashed into fine powder, prior to further utilization. The obtained biomass was mixed with urea and/or boric

acid at the w/w ratio of 1:1, dispersed in water and sonicated for 0.5 h. Afterwards, the mixture was subjected to high energy ball-milling treatment at 300 rpm for 1h (FRITSCH Planetary Mono Mill Pulverisette 6), dried overnight and annealed in a tube furnace at 600°C for 2 h under the flow of N₂ (110 mL/min) with the heating rate of 10°C/min. The product was washed with ultrapure water, dried in an oven at 80°C and stored in a desiccator for subsequent use. The synthesized metal-free carbocatalysts were denoted as N-doped 600, B-doped 600, and N,B-codoped 600, according to the present type of dopant(s).

Catalytic oxidation experiments

The catalytic oxidation experiments were performed in a 250 ml beaker containing 100 mL of water solution model mixture (10 µg/L concentration of each compound) – 11 pesticides and 11 PhACs at 25°C. In each experiment, 100 mg of catalyst and 135 mg K₂S₂O₈ were added into the reaction solution and stirred at 600 rpm. At designated time intervals, 1 mL aliquots of reaction solution were withdrawn and filtered through a Nylon syringe filter with a pore size of 0.22 µm. The obtained filtrates (0.5 mL) were immediately mixed with 0.5 mL methanol in order to quench the reaction. The residual concentrations of CECs were analysed by high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (UHPLC–MS/MS, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) (Rakić et al., 2023).

Results and discussion

The catalytic activity of the synthesized heteroatom-doped samples of pyrochar was assessed by coupling with PDS in a water solution model mixture containing 11 selected pesticides and 11 PhACs. Figure 1 represents the removal efficiencies of the tested CECs in three different catalytic systems after 90 min of oxidation process.

Figure 1. Removal efficiencies (%) of selected a) pesticides and b) PhACs in the presence of heteroatom-doped carbocatalysts after 90 min of oxidation process

As seen in Figure 1, all tested carbocatalysts exhibited superior performance for the degradation of PhACs, compared to the selected pesticides. Omethoat and trichlorfon were not prone to oxidation in the presence of any doped pyrochar, while B-doped sample was completely inactive towards methamidophos also (Figure 1a). A relatively poor reactivity of N-doped pyrochar at the end of the process was observed in the case of phosphamidon (25.2% removal efficiency, Figure 1a). The same catalyst showed moderate oxidation ability for carbofuran, acetamiprid, ethoprophos, dimethoate, and methamidophos, while in the case of methidation, imazalil, and diazinon, a significantly enhanced removal was noted (>80%, Figure 1a). The improvement of catalytic performance with the introduction of boron species in the carbon structure along with the nitrogen ones was recorded in the case of all tested pesticides, except methamidophos with 2.5 times reduced degradation degree (Figure 1a). In the N,B-codoped system, four pesticides (diazinon, acetamiprid, imazalil and methidathion) were almost completely removed after 90 min of process (Figure 1a). Although stimulating effect of N,B-codoping on the PDS activation capacity of pyrochar towards pesticides was verified, a substantial enhancement in PDS activation was achieved with sole boron-doping pyrochar. In the simultaneous presence of B-doped 600 catalyst and PDS, an excellent degradation of eight pesticides was accomplished, whereas seven of them were almost 100% catalytically oxidized (Figure 1a). The results of PhACs removal efficiencies (Figure 1b) indicated the captivating prospect of heteroatom-doped pyrochar as an excellent metal-free catalyst. Nitrogen containing species were catalytically active gaining 100% removal of seven tested PhACs, while moderate performance was achieved only in the case of atenolol (Figure 1b). The beneficial aspect of codoping, compared to N-doping, in terms of boosting the catalytic activity, can also be observed for PhACs, with the exception of sotalol and clarithromycin (Figure 1b). The boron-doped carbocatalyst can be regarded as the superb one for all tested PhACs with 100% oxidation ability (93.8% only in the case of atenolol, Figure 1b).

Figure 2. Degradation kinetics of CECs in heteroatom-doped carbocatalysts/PDS system

Catalytic performances of heteroatom-doped carbocatalysts were evaluated by the removal of selected CECs during 90 min of oxidation process. The experimental data (Figure 2) were fitted to the pseudo first-order kinetics as follows: $C = C_0 e^{-k_{app}t}$, where C and C_0 are the concentrations of each individual pollutant at time t and 0 min, respectively, and k_{app} is the

pseudo first-order rate constant. According to the obtained kinetic data, it can be observed that the tested catalytic systems result in the disparity in the degradation trend in terms of the applied type of catalyst, as well as the category of CECs. In the presence of N-doped 600, methamidophos starts to decompose after 15 min, while imazalil, diazinon and methidathion exhibit an initial rapid degradation rate being 87%, 68%, and 55% removed, respectively, during the first 5 min of process. The continuation of the process can be characterized by low degradation rate with constant k_{app} of 0.01 min^{-1} for both diazinon and methidathion. Dimethoate displays a relatively consistent degradation rate during the whole process ($k_{app} = 0.01 \text{ min}^{-1}$), while acetamiprid, carbofuran and ethoprophos are being degraded very slowly with k_{app} below 0.007 min^{-1} after 10 min. In the codoped/PDS catalytic system, the highest quantity of the present pesticides (except diazinon with k_{app} of 0.04 min^{-1} during the whole time interval) has been removed after 15 min followed by a very low degradation rate. An exceptionally rapid degradation of seven selected pesticides was observed for the B-doped pyrochar with more than 80% removal efficiency after 5 min of simultaneous exposure to catalyst and PDS. The degradation trend of atenolol, sotalol, ofloxacin, carbamazepine, and salbutamol, catalyzed by sole N-species, can be portrayed by relatively consistent rates with k_{app} of 0.008 min^{-1} , 0.030 min^{-1} , 0.008 min^{-1} , 0.010 min^{-1} and 0.030 min^{-1} , respectively. Other examined PhACs are almost completely degraded after 15 min of oxidation. The combination of N- and B-active centers in pyrochar structure initiates the fast oxidation of 9 PhACs at the beginning of the process, with the highest amount of each contaminants being degraded within 15 min. Salbutamol and ofloxacin (same value of $k_{app} = 0.02 \text{ min}^{-1}$) have different kinetic profile with constant decline of concentration till the end of the process. The excellent catalytic performance of B-doped carbocatalyst towards all 11 PhACs is reflected in the rate of their degradation since 8 PhACs are completely removed from the system within 5 min.

Conclusions

In summary, pinewood sawdust, as an abundant carbon precursor and cheap urea and boric acid were adopted for the preparation of heteroatom-doped metal-free green catalysts *via* facile and scalable one-step pyrolysis process. Experimental results demonstrated that both single-doped (N- and B-doped), as well as the codoped pyrochar (N,B-doped) exhibit very good PDS activation capacity towards 20 out of 22 selected CECs, possessing superior catalytic performance for the degradation of PhACs compared to the tested pesticides. B-doped pyrochar out-performed the other two catalysts gaining very rapid and almost complete removal of 7 pesticides and all PhACs for 90 min of oxidation process. This study provides a green and feasible approach to produce metal-free carbonaceous persulfate activators for highly efficient degradation of various CECs with a great potential to be implemented in practice.

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References

- Anfar, Z., Ait El Fakir, A., Zbair, M., Hafidi, Z., Amedlous, A., Majdoub, M., Farsad, S., Amjlef, A., Jada, A., El Alem, N. (2021). New functionalization approach synthesis of Sulfur doped, Nitrogen doped and Co-doped porous carbon: Superior metal-free Carbocatalyst for the catalytic oxidation of aqueous organics pollutants. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 405, 126660.
- Duan, X., Sun, H., Wang, S. (2018). Metal-free carbocatalysis in advanced oxidation reactions. *Accounts of Chemical Research*, 51, 678–687.
- Feng, W., Deng, Y., Yang, F., Miao, Q., Ngien, S.K. (2023). Systematic Review of Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs): Distribution, Risks, and Implications for Water Quality and Health. *Water*, 15, 3922.
- Ghanbari, F., Moradi, M. (2017). Application of peroxymonosulfate and its activation methods for degradation of environmental organic pollutants: Review. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 310, 41-62.
- Hu, W., Xie, Y., Lu, S., Li, P., Xie, T., Zhang, Y., Wang, Y. (2019). One-step synthesis of nitrogen-doped sludge carbon as a bifunctional material for the adsorption and catalytic oxidation of organic pollutants. *Science of The Total Environment*, 680, 51-60.
- Liu, B., Li, Y., Wu, Y., Xing, S. (2021). Enhanced degradation of ofloxacin by persulfate activation with Mn doped CuO: synergetic effect between adsorption and non-radical activation. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 417, 127972.
- Liu, W.-J., Jiang, H., Yu, H.-Q. (2015). Development of biochar-based functional materials: toward a sustainable platform carbon material. *Chemical Reviews*, 115, 12251–12285.
- Oh, W.-D., Dong, Z., Lim, T.-T. (2016). Generation of sulfate radical through heterogeneous catalysis for organic contaminants removal: Current development, challenges and prospects. *Applied Catalysis B: Environmental*, 194, 169-201.
- Rakić, D., Antić, I., Živančev, J., Buljovčić, M., Šereš, Z., Đurišić-Mladenović, N. (2023). Solid-phase extraction as promising sample preparation method for compound of emerging concerns analysis. *Analecta Technica Szegedinensia*, 17(4), 16-24.
- Wang, W. Q., Chen, M. (2022). Catalytic degradation of sulfamethoxazole by peroxymonosulfate activation system composed of nitrogen-doped biochar from pomelo peel: important roles of defects and nitrogen, and detoxification of intermediates. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 613, 57–70.
- Ye, F., Shi, Y., Sun, W., Pang, K., Pu, M., Yang, L., Huang, H. (2023). Construction of adsorption-oxidation bifunction-oriented carbon by single boron doping for non-radical antibiotic degradation via persulfate activation. *Chemical Engineering Journal*, 454, 140148.
- Zaeni, J.R.J., Lim, J.-W., Wang, Z., Ding, D., Chua, Y.-S., Ng, S.-L., Oh, W.-D. (2020). In situ nitrogen functionalization of biochar via one-pot synthesis for catalytic peroxymonosulfate activation: Characteristics and performance studies. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 241, 116702.

REMOVAL OF ACETAMINOPHEN AND CLARITHROMYCIN FROM WATER SAMPLES USING NANOFILTRATION AND REVERSE OSMOSIS

***Nikola Maravić^{1*}, Zita Šereš¹, Jelena Šurlan¹, Nataša Đurišić Mladenović¹, Igor Antić¹, Jelena Živančev¹,
Carla Brazinha², Claudia F. Galinha², João G. Crespo^{2,3}***

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology, Bul. cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia

²LAQV-REQUIMTE, DQ, FCT NOVA, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, 2829-516 Caparica, Portugal

³ITQB, Universidade NOVA de Lisboa, Av. da República, 2780-157 Oeiras, Portugal

*maravic@uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Acetaminophen and clarithromycin are both contaminants of emerging concern in water systems due to their widespread use and incomplete removal by conventional wastewater treatment processes. Pharmaceuticals such as acetaminophen and clarithromycin can easily enter surface water systems through the disposal of unused medications or via excretion.

Polyamide membranes for both reverse osmosis, SW30HR (Filmtec, USA), and nanofiltration, NF270 (Filmtec, USA), were used for investigating removal of corresponding two pharmaceuticals. All experiments were conducted in METCell® dead-end unit (EVONIK, Germany). This study investigated the impact of pH on the rejection rates of acetaminophen and clarithromycin by SW30HR and NF270 membranes. The results showed that at pH 4, both membranes exhibit higher rejection rates for clarithromycin compared to acetaminophen. However, at pH 10, NF270 membrane showed significantly higher rejection rates for acetaminophen compared to the experiments conducted at pH 4 and pH 7. On the contrary, clarithromycin showed different trend with the rising pH value in NF270 experiments. SW30HR membrane rejection rates of all tested pharmaceuticals are higher in all experiments confirming hypothesis of dominating size exclusion mechanism in the investigated reverse osmosis process. These findings highlight the pH-dependent behavior of the membranes in rejecting pharmaceutical compounds, which could be crucial in designing efficient membrane processes for pharmaceutical wastewater treatment.

Keywords: Acetaminophen, Clarithromycin, Reverse osmosis, Nanofiltration, Polyamide.

Introduction

Emergent microcontaminants and their metabolites, which represent a significant risk for the environment and human health, can be found more and more frequently in the aquatic environment (Loss et al., 2009; Richardson & Kimura, 2016). Emergent microcontaminants include pharmaceuticals, pesticides, synthetic and natural hormones, additives, plasticizers, flame retardants, as well as personal hygiene products (Richardson & Ternes, 2011; Rizzo et al., 2019). Pharmaceuticals are various organic compounds that, due to their widespread use, are often detected in aquatic systems. The harmful impact of pharmaceuticals on the environment is a consequence of their incomplete metabolism in the body, as well as wide and frequent use, therefore they can be found in the environment in their original form or as active metabolites of the original component (Zhang et al., 2008; Gouveia et al., 2023). Due to their wide use, among the most frequently detected pharmaceuticals are different antibiotics, antipyretic, anesthetics, etc. Their frequent detection in treated wastewater indicated the inefficiency of current water purification techniques in removing pharmaceuticals, therefore, efforts are being made to develop new techniques and methods for their removal (Anumol et al., 2016). Various methods, such as membrane filtration,

activated sludge treatments, ozonation and advanced oxidation processes, are receiving more attention in order to remove pharmaceuticals from aquatic environments (Crespo & Bøddeker, 2013). Research has shown the high efficiency of nanofiltration in the removal of pharmaceuticals and other emergent microcontaminants (Sanchez et al., 2012). The aim of this study was to investigate the impact of pH and pharmaceutical molecular weight as well as other molecular descriptors on the rejection rates of acetaminophen and clarithromycin by using polyamide membranes for reverse osmosis (SW30HR) and nanofiltration (NF270).

Materials and methods

Sample preparation

High purity acetaminophen and clarithromycin standards were used for sample preparation were purchased from Sigma Aldrich (St. Louis, MO, USA) or LGC (Augsburg, Germany). LC-MS grade methanol (MeOH) (Radnor, USA), was used for the preparation of stock solutions as well as in solid phase extraction (SPE) for adsorbent conditioning and elution. Ultrapure (Milli Q) water (18 MΩ cm), was used for sample solution preparation. Sodium hydroxide (0.1 g mol⁻¹) and hydrochloric acid (0.1 g mol⁻¹) solutions were used for pH adjustment of prepared model solutions. Sample solutions were prepared by spiking the stock solution with acetaminophen and clarithromycin in 200 mL Milli Q water. Concentration in model solution was set 300 ng L⁻¹. Additionally, sodium chloride was added in a reverse osmosis sample solution at pH 7 in order to determine the influence of added salt on rejection of CECs.

2.2 Nanofiltration and reverse osmosis experiments

Polyamide membranes for both reverse osmosis, SW30HR (Filmtec, USA), and nanofiltration, NF270 (Filmtec, USA), were used for investigating removal of corresponding two pharmaceuticals. All experiments were conducted in METCell® dead-end unit (EVONIK, Germany). Membranes were selected based on the differences in molecular weight cut offs (MWCO) (NF 270 – MWCO 400Da and SW30HR – MWCA 100Da). Prior to conducting the experiments, membranes were soaked in ultrapure water for 24 hours. The pressure was set at 3 bar and 30 bar for NF270 and SW30HR membranes, respectively. Membrane flux was set at a constant value of 5.88 mL h⁻¹ cm⁻² for the duration of the experiments and monitored for the duration of the experiments by acquisition of the permeate weight with an accuracy of 0.01 g.

Concentrations of targeted compounds were analyzed in the feed, permeate and retentate. One membrane was used for experiments at three pH values. In between experiments, membranes and the dead-end unit were cleaned with large amounts of ultrapure water.

Removal of CECs was presented as rejection factor R (%) and was calculated using the following equation:

$$R=(1-c_p/c_r)*100 \quad (1)$$

where c_r and c_p represent CECs concentration (ng/mL) in retentate and permeate, respectively.

Obtained samples (feed, permeate and retentate), were loaded on SPE cartridges and were eluted from SPE cartridges with 2 x 4 mL of MeOH and the obtained eluates were evaporated to dryness at 30 °C under a nitrogen stream and reconstituted in 1 mL of first gradient mobile phase. High performance liquid chromatography coupled with triple

quadrupole mass spectrometry, UHPLC-MS/MS, (Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) was used for instrumental analysis of selected CECs. Spray voltage, vaporizer temperature, and capillary temperature of the ion source were set at 3.4 kV, 250°C, and 270°C, respectively. Sheath gas pressure and auxiliary gas pressure of the ion source were set at 40 (arbitrary units) and 10 (arbitrary units), respectively.

Results and discussion

The table 1 presents the rejection rates of acetaminophen and clarithromycin at different pH levels using two types of membranes: NF270 (nanofiltration) and SW30HR (reverse osmosis). The data indicates how the efficacy of these membranes varies with the pH of the aqueous solution and the type of pharmaceutical compound. For acetaminophen, the rejection rate varies strongly between the two different membranes and across the investigated pH values. The lowest rejection value was obtained in the nanofiltration process at pH 4 (46.57%) while the highest rejection value was obtained in the reverse osmosis experiments by using water solution of pH 7 and 10 (above 92%). Furthermore, evident differences could be noticed when using water samples of different pH values within the experiments of the single membrane. The biggest increase is noticed in the experiments where NF270 was used. By increasing pH values from 4 to 10, the rejection rate is doubled (46.57% to 91,6%) suggesting specific mechanisms of rejection in acidic and alkaline solutions. Similar results are obtained when using reverse osmosis membrane (SW30HR) for filtration of acetaminophen but with smaller differences in rejection values (78.89% to 92.08%). Overall, the SW30HR reverse osmosis membrane demonstrates consistently high rejection rates for acetaminophen across all pH values, outperforming the NF270 nanofiltration membrane, especially at lower pH levels.

Table 1. Rejection rate of acetaminophen and clarithromycin

Chemical compound	pH value	Rejection (%)	
		NF270	SW30HR
Acetaminophen	pH 4	46.57	78.89
	pH 7	49.35	92.71
	pH 10	91.6	92.08
Clarithromycin	pH 4	91.67	93.01
	pH 7	95.76	89.03
	pH 10	52.67	89.72

By taking molecular weight of acetaminophen into consideration (molecular weight of acetaminophen is around 151.2Da), different rejection rates of NF270 and SW30HR are expected. NF270 has 4 times higher MWCO comparing to SW30HR, 400Da to 100Da, respectively, which highly influenced the rejection of relatively small pharmaceutical compound like acetaminophen. However, the changes in water samples pH value towards alkaline area highlighted the possible changes in molecular structure and interaction which increased the rejection rate and lowered the amount of acetaminophen in permeate samples.

The rejection rate regarding clarithromycin didn't vary strongly between the two different membranes but across the investigated pH values. The lowest rejection value was obtained in the nanofiltration process at pH 10 (52.67%) while the highest rejection value was obtained in the nanofiltration experiments by using water solution of pH 7 (95.76%). However, differences between the experiments using different membranes were not evident as in the previously discussed rejection of acetaminophen. Furthermore, evident differences could only be easily noticed in comparing nanofiltration experiment at pH 10 to all other conducted runs. Nanofiltration of clarithromycin at pH 10 showed the lowest value of rejection which is in contrast to the trend observed in acetaminophen experiments. Since the clarithromycin and acetaminophen have almost similar pKa values (8.99 and 9.38, respectively) the possible changes in membrane surface would impact rejection in the similar direction. Therefore, the obtained results could indicate stronger impact on molecular structure rather than changes in membrane surface which influenced unexpected lower rejection rate of clarithromycin, even though clarithromycin MW is almost five times higher compared to acetaminophen.

Conclusions

The presented study demonstrated that the SW30HR reverse osmosis membrane consistently achieved high rejection rates for acetaminophen across all pH values, outperforming the NF270 nanofiltration membrane, particularly at lower pH values. The NF270 membrane exhibited considerable variability in rejection rates, increasing from 46.57% at pH 4 to 91.6% at pH 10, suggesting specific rejection mechanisms at different pH conditions. Overall, the SW30HR membrane showed more effective for the removal of pharmaceuticals in diverse pH environments, delivering higher and more stable rejection rates. Rejection rate of clarithromycin varied across different pH levels but not between different membranes. The results suggest that pharmaceutical molecular structure, rather than membrane surface changes, played a crucial role in its rejection.

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References

- Anumol, T., Vijayanandan, A., Park, M., Philip, L., & Snyder, S. A. (2016). Occurrence and fate of emerging trace organic chemicals in wastewater plants in Chennai, India. *Environment international*, 92, 33-42.
- Crespo, J. G., & Bøddeker, K. W. (Eds.). (2013). *Membrane processes in separation and purification* (Vol. 272). Springer Science & Business Media.

Gouveia, T. I., Cristóvão, M. B., Pereira, V. J., Crespo, J. G., Alves, A., Ribeiro, A. R., ... & Santos, M. S. (2023). Antineoplastic drugs in urban wastewater: occurrence, nanofiltration treatment and toxicity screening. *Environmental Pollution*, 332, 121944.

Loos, R., Gawlik, B. M., Locoro, G., Rimaviciute, E., Contini, S., & Bidoglio, G. (2009). EU-wide survey of polar organic persistent pollutants in European river waters. *Environmental pollution*, 157(2), 561-568.

Richardson, S. D., & Kimura, S. Y. (2016). Water analysis: emerging contaminants and current issues. *Analytical chemistry*, 88(1), 546-582.

Richardson, S. D., & Ternes, T. A. (2011). Water analysis: emerging contaminants and current issues. *Analytical chemistry*, 83(12), 4614-4648.

Rizzo, L., Malato, S., Antakyali, D., Beretsou, V. G., Đolić, M. B., Gernjak, W., ... & Fatta Kassinos, D. (2019). Consolidated vs new advanced treatment methods for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern from urban wastewater. *Science of the Total Environment*, 655, 986-1008.

Sanches, S., Penetra, A., Rodrigues, A., Ferreira, E., Cardoso, V. V., Benoliel, M. J., ... & Crespo, J. G. (2012). Nanofiltration of hormones and pesticides in different real drinking water sources. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 94, 44-53.

Zhang, Z., Hibberd, A., & Zhou, J. L. (2008). Analysis of emerging contaminants in sewage effluent and river water: comparison between spot and passive sampling. *Analytica chimica acta*, 607(1), 37-44.

SEWAGE SLUDGE BIOCHAR AS A SORBENT FOR CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERNS REMOVAL FROM WATER

Vesna M. Vasić**, *Dragana V. Lukić*, *Marina B. Šćiban

University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bul. cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia,

**vesna.vasic@uns.ac.rs*

Abstract

The continuous release of contaminants of emerging concerns (CECs) into the environment has been recognized as a danger to the ecosystem and human health. Through sewage, these compounds reach the wastewater treatment plants, which are ineffective in the CECs removal, so they remain in the effluent and are discharged into the water bodies. Thus, it is necessary to evaluate and develop effective technologies for the remediation of CECs. Biosorption is one of the most promising low-cost techniques for water treatment. In recent years, various materials have been tested as biosorbents, and more recently, attention has been drawn to sewage sludge as a raw material for biochar production, which may be promising from the viewpoint of circular economy and waste management. In recent years, the quantity of sewage sludge has been increasing globally, due to the increased number of wastewater treatment plants, so the need to manage this waste has become an important issue. This paper will summarize the state of the art on the application of sewage sludge biochar as an adsorbent for CECs removal from water. It is obvious from the literature that specific properties and porous structure make it suitable for the removal of contaminants from water.

Keywords: Sewage sludge, CECs, Biochar, Wastewater treatment.

Introduction

The continuous release of contaminants of emerging concern in nature represents an emerging threat to biodiversity. Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) are the main source of CEC, considering that conventional treatment in urban WWTPs is not effective in the removal of these compounds. In this way, contaminants often appear in water resources, so water quality is increasingly connected to the quality of wastewater. Regarding that most CECs are still not regulated, a big challenge is in front of scientists, policymakers, and industry players.

Considering that the costs of wastewater treatment are increasing and that the requirements regarding their purification are increasingly strict, it is necessary to emphasize methods that will enable the reuse of these waters. Regarding the CECs removal, many issues must be taken into account (social, economic, ecological). Different advanced treatment technologies have been studied and developed for the removal of these compounds from water and wastewater. However, they are still present in the environment and threaten human health. One of the novel developments is the production of biochar from sewage sludge, that can be used as an efficient biosorbent for water remediation. Its utilization for the removal of emerging contaminants has been investigated in recent years, and this paper will summarise the state-of-the-art sewage sludge biochar research describing achievement in CECs remediation.

Sewage sludge

Wastewater treatment solves one of the most important environmental issues but at the same time arises another one – sewage sludge. Sewage sludge is a semi-solid byproduct generated during the purification of wastewater, and it contains pollution from wastewater which is returned to the environment through sludge disposal. It is expected that the amount of sludge will increase significantly at the global level, due to increasingly strict requirements for the quality of the effluent discharged into recipients, and the building of new wastewater treatment plants (Barry et al., 2019). Therefore, it is necessary to develop a strategy for handling such waste. When treating sludge, special attention must be taken to ensure that sludge is handled according to the principle of sustainable handling, which in this case would mean recycling sludge as a resource, in that way that harmful substances from sludge do not endanger human health or the environment.

The options for the treatment of sewage sludge include incineration, landfilling, and agricultural applications. The disposal of sewage sludge can be expensive and cause problems because of significant concentrations of toxic metals, organic contaminants, microplastics, and pathogens. Also, during incineration greenhouse gases, fly ash, and PAHs are released (Krahn et al., 2023). In the last decade, sludge has attracted attention as a raw material for the production of biochar which can be used for various applications including soil amendment and water and wastewater treatment as an economically and environmentally sustainable waste management solution.

Sewage sludge is a waste that contributes a high carbon emission to the atmosphere, which is increasing worldwide since conventional processing of this waste is still applied in most countries. Production of biochar by pyrolysis is one of the strategies that can significantly reduce carbon emissions. Pyrolysis is the thermal decomposition process of organic matter at elevated temperatures (400-800°C) in the absence of oxygen (Adamović et al., 2023). During the pyrolysis solid organic matter is transformed into biochar, condensable vapor product (bio-oil), and gas products (Barry et al., 2019). Research has shown that SSBC is a suitable material for carbon sequestration, water purification, and greenhouse gas reduction. Some authors (Sun et al. (2022), Woolf et al. (2021)) reported the results of a study that included quantification of the carbon footprint of the entire process of sewage sludge pyrolysis to biochar. These findings indicate that pyrolysis is a promising alternative for sewage sludge treatment and thus greatly impacts achieving carbon neutrality.

Sewage sludge biochar sorbents

The composition of sewage sludge biochar depends on the type of pyrolysis, the composition of the feedstock, temperature, and residence time. Generally, it is mainly composed of organic carbon, while the inorganic compounds are Ca, Mg, K, P, metals, etc. (Racek et al., 2020). Its specific chemical composition in terms of mineral components and presence of functional groups, large surface area, and porosity make it suitable as an adsorbent for the removal of emerging pollutants from water (table 1). Literature data indicate that various sewage sludge-based adsorbents have been developed and examined for the removal of different contaminants from wastewater (Singh et al., 2020).

The most recent study (Mohamed et al., 2023) showed very good efficiencies of sewage sludge biochar for polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs, alkyl-PAHs) and polybrominated diphenyl ethers (PBDs) removal from wastewater treatment plant effluent. Removal efficiency for PAHs was 88-100%, and for PBDs was 52-100%. Similar results were reported by Montoya-Bautista et al. (2023) for the removal of pharmaceutical and personal care products (PPCPs), phthalates, and alkylphenol from secondary effluent. The use of sewage sludge biochar sorbents for per - and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) removal from water was examined by Krahn et al. (2023). This study compared two sewage sludge biochar (SSBCs) and wood chip biochar (WCBC) adsorption properties for the removal of six perfluorinated carboxylic acids (PFCAs). Results showed that adsorption effectiveness was better for sewage sludge biochar than wood-based biochar, and indicated that the strong sorption of PFCAs was attributed to relatively high pore volumes of SSBCs in the pore size range that can capture these compounds. Another confirmation of the successful application of sewage sludge biochar for CECs removal from water and wastewater was reported by Regkouzas and Diamadopoulus (2019). The application of SSBCs produced from three different sludge biomasses for the removal of seven emerging contaminants from table water and secondary effluent was investigated. The removal rate of selected contaminants was in the range of 67-99% for the table water and 35-97% for the wastewater.

Table 1. Sewage sludge-based adsorbents for the removal of emerging pollutants from water

Adsorbent	Pollutant	Removal efficiency	References
Sewage sludge BC	2,4 – Dichlorophenol	100%	Kalderis et al., 2017
Sewage sludge BC	Fulvic acids	93-96 mg/g	Konczak, et al. 2021
Sewage sludge BC, Produced at 500°C	Bisphenol A Carbamazepine Estrone 17a-Ethinylestradiol 2, 4-Dichlorophenol 2, 3, 4-Trichlorophenol	90-99%	Regkouzas and Diamadopoulus (2019)
Sewage sludge BC containing Fe	Tetracycline	90.3%	Kang et al., 2023

The chemical composition of sewage sludge biochar varies significantly depending on the origin of the sludge and pyrolysis conditions. High surface area, porosity, and carbon content are key for the sorption of organic contaminants from water, therefore the optimization of the pyrolysis conditions is very important when we talk about the production of efficient biosorbents. Figueiredo et al. (201), evaluated the influence of pyrolysis temperature on the chemical and physical properties of sewage sludge biochar. It was found that the surface area of sludge-based biochar increased with increasing temperature. At low temperatures, organic volatiles condense and cause clogging of the pores, so the surface area available for adsorption decreases. Contrary to that, volatilization that happens at high temperatures makes the biochar more porous.

The effect of pyrolysis temperature and activation processes on sewage sludge adsorption performances for the removal of tetracycline was investigated by Liu et al. (2020, 2021). The results showed that the pyrolysis temperature has a high impact on biochar properties, and the specific surface area of the biochar initially increased and then decreased with an increase in the temperature. In these studies, tetracycline adsorption was improved from 94.69 to 379.78 mg/g by upgrading biochar surface area and porosity.

Conclusion

According to the results of different reported studies, it can be said that sewage sludge biochar has a high potential as a low-cost biosorbent, it can be used for the removal of different pollutants from wastewater and represents a sustainable solution for the remediation of CECs, and waste management. However, many authors emphasize other challenges that should be taken into consideration when talking about this topic, namely the costs of the entire process, modification of biochar to increase the efficiency of wastewater treatment, understanding the mechanisms of pollutant binding, as well as filling the gap between research stage and commercialization.

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References

- Adamović, A., Petronijević, M., Panić, S., Cvetković, D., Antic, I., Petrović, Z. & Đurišić-Mladenović, N. (2023). Biochar and hydrochar as adsorbents for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern from wastewater. *Advanced Technologies*, 12, 57-74.
- Barry, D., Barbiero, C., Briens, C. & Berruti, F. (2019). Pyrolysis as an economical and ecological treatment option for municipal sewage sludge. *Biomass and Bioenergy* 122, 472-480.
- Figueiredo, C., Lopes, H., Coser, T., Vale, A., Busato, J., Aguiar, N., Novotny, E. & Canellas, L. (2018) Influence of pyrolysis temperature on chemical and physical properties of biochar from sewage sludge. *Archives of Agronomy and Soil Science*, 64, 881-889.
- Kalderis, D., Kayan, B., Akay, S., Kulaksız, E. & Gözmen B. (2017). Adsorption of 2,4-dichlorophenol on paper sludge/wheat husk biochar: process optimization and comparison with biochars prepared from woodchips, sewage sludge and hog fuel/demolition waste. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 5, 2222–2231.
- Kang, X., Zhang, Q., Liu, X., Song, J., Guo, H. & Wang, L. (2023). The interface mechanisms of sludge biochar activating persulfate to remove tetracycline: the role of C-O-Fe bridge at the carbon surface. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 384, 135514.

Konczak, M., Siatecka, A., Nazarkovsky, M.A., Czech, B. & Oleszczuk, P. (2021). Sewage sludge and soil residues from biogas production derived biochar as an effective biowaste adsorbent of fulvic acids from water or wastewater. *Chemosphere*, 278, 130447.

Krahn, K.M., Cornelissen, G., Castro, G., Arp, H.P.H., Asimakopoulos, A.G., Wolf, R., Holmstad, R., Zimmerman, A.R. & Sørmo, E. (2023). Sewage sludge biochars as effective PFAS-sorbents. *Journal of Hazardous Materials*, 445, 130449.

Liu, H., XU, G. & Li, G. (2020). The characteristics of pharmaceutical sludge-derived biochar and its application for the adsorption of tetracycline. *Science of the Total Environment*, 747, 141492.

Liu, H., XU, G. & Li, G. (2021). Preparation of porous biochar based on pharmaceutical sludge activated by NaOH and its application in the adsorption of tetracycline. *Journal of Colloid and Interface Science*, 587, 271-278.

Mohamed, B.A., Hamid, H., Montoya-Bautista, C.V. & Li, L.Y. (2023). Circular economy in wastewater treatment plants: Treatment of contaminants of emerging concerns (CECs) in effluent using sludge-based activated carbon. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 389, 136095.

Montoya-Bautista, C.V., Mohamed, B.A., & Li, L.Y. (2022). Sludge-based activated carbon from two municipal sewage sludge precursors for improved secondary wastewater treatment. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 10, 108704.

Racek, J., Sevcik, J., Chorazy, T., Kucerik, J. & Hlavinek, P. (2020). Biochar – Recovery Material from Pyrolysis of Sewage Sludge: A Review. *Waste and Biomass Valorization*, 11:3677-3709.

Regkouzas, P. & Diamadopoulos, E. (2019). Adsorption of selected organic micro-pollutants on sewage sludge biochar. *Chemosphere*, 224, 840-851.

Singh, S., Kumar, V., Singh Dhanjal, D., Datta, S., Bhatia, D., Dhiman, J., Samuel, J., Prasad, R. & Singh, J. (2020). A sustainable paradigm of sewage sludge biochar: Valorization, opportunities, challenges and future prospects. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 269, 122259.

Sun, H., Luo, L., Wang, D., Liu, W., Lan, Y., Yang, T., Gai, C. & Liu, Z. (2022). Carbon balance analysis of sewage sludge biochar-to-soil system. *Journal of Cleaner Production*, 358, 132057.

Woolf, D., Lehmann, J., Ogle, S., Kishimoto-Mo, A.W., McConkey, B. & Baldock, J. (2021). Greenhouse Gas Inventory Model for Biochar Additions to Soil. *Environmental Science and Technology*, 55, 14795-14805.

MULTICOMPONENT ADSORPTION KINETICS OF MICROPOLLUTANTS ONTO LIGNOCELLULOSIC BIOSORBENTS

Dragana Lukić*, Vesna Vasić, Marina Šćiban, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović, Igor Antić, Jelena Živančev

¹University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bul. cara Lazara 1, 21 000 Novi Sad, Serbia,

**dkukic@uns.ac.rs*

Abstract

The removal of micropollutants represents a major challenge due to their low concentrations, complex mixtures, and diverse sources of contamination. Innovative wastewater treatment technologies for the efficient removal of CECs have their advantages and limitations, and the research community is making an effort to optimize their performance, cost-effectiveness, and applicability for widespread implementation. Due to the high cost of the adsorption process, the focus of active research in this area is the development of effective and novel materials for pollutant removal.

In this paper, raspberry cane and lignin isolated from this waste material were investigated as potential biosorbents for the removal of chemicals of emerging concern from a synthetic mixture. The multi-component adsorption kinetics of 35 different compounds was carried out in a batch mode. Biosorbents were mixed with a synthetic mixture with an initial concentration of each compound of about 30 µg/l for 24 hours. At different time intervals, an aliquot of the mixture was taken and residual concentrations of CECs were determined. The results revealed that the same 14 compounds showed no adsorption on both of the investigated biosorbents. The rest of the CECs appeared to be adsorbed fast, mostly during the first 60 min of the process. For 11 compounds removal was over 80% either by raspberry canes or lignin. However, lignin appeared to be generally slightly more efficient.

Keywords: Micropollutants, Wastewater treatment, Biosorption, Raspberry cane, Lignin.

Introduction

Chemicals of emerging concern (CECs) are a group of environmental pollutants that include a wide range of naturally occurring substances and synthetic chemicals such as pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides, and industrial chemicals. They are often defined as compounds not included in existing water quality legislation or monitoring programs. Over the past few decades, their presence in water bodies has raised concerns due to potentially harmful effects on human health and the environment (Arous et al., 2019; Vasić et al., 2023). Some studies report high rates of bioaccumulation of some CECs with endocrine-disrupting effects in aquatic organisms and the possibility of entering into the food chain. Exposure to this group of micropollutants can interfere with the growth and normal functioning of living beings while antibiotics can affect antimicrobial resistance (González-González et al., 2022). The release of CECs into the environment has been occurring for a long time (Prangya, 2021), but the development of analytical techniques for detecting low concentrations of these compounds brought them into the focus of interest. As a result, nowadays, research on micropollutants mainly deals with the detection and removal techniques.

One of the primary pathways of micropollutants to water bodies is wastewater discharge since traditional wastewater treatment is inefficient in their removal (Alexa et al., 2022). Unlike conventional pollutants, such as organic matter and nutrients, micropollutants represent a major challenge due to their low concentrations, complex mixtures, and different physico-chemical characteristics. Innovative wastewater treatment technologies for removing CECs include advanced oxidation processes, membrane filtration, and adsorption (Vasić et

al., 2023a). Each of these technologies has some advantages and limitations, and the research community is making an effort to optimize their performance, cost-effectiveness, and applicability for widespread implementation.

In this context, for a better understanding of the behavior of micropollutants in complex mixtures, the kinetics of adsorption on lignocellulosic biosorbents was investigated. A synthetic mixture of 35 CECs including pharmaceutical compounds, insecticides, pesticides, and herbicides, of neutral pH was used in batch adsorption experiments. Lignin isolated from raspberry canes and raspberry canes, earlier reported as potential biosorbents for CECs removal (Vasić et al., 2023b; Lukić et al., 2023), were further investigated as biosorbents.

Materials and methods

Biosorbents

Raspberry canes (RCs) of Willamette species were collected at a local field and left to dry at room temperature. Dried RCs were milled on a Miag Braunschweig DOXY 71b/4 mill and sieved through a set of sieves (BÜHLER MLU – 300) to obtain 224-400 µm fraction. Lignin from RCs was isolated by dioxane procedure (Lourenço et al., 2022).

Batch adsorption experiments

A synthetic mixture of 35 CECs including pharmaceuticals, insecticides, and pesticides with an initial concentration of each compound of about 30 µg/l was prepared in ultra-pure water. Adsorption experiments were performed by mixing 0.5 g of each biosorbent with 500 ml of the synthetic mixture on a magnetic stirrer for 24 hours. At different time intervals (5, 10, 20, 30, 60, 90, 180, 360 min, and 24 h) 1 ml of the mixture was taken with a syringe and filtrated through a PTFE syringe filter with a pore size of 0.22 µm. In the obtained filtrates the residual concentrations of CECs were analyzed by high-performance liquid chromatography coupled to triple quadrupole mass spectrometry (UHPLC–MS/MS, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) (Rakić et al., 2023).

Experimental data were fitted using pseudo-first (Ofomaja, 2010) and second-order kinetic models (Ho et al., 1995).

Results and discussion

The contact time of adsorbent and adsorbate plays an important role in adsorption. It is essential to determine the time necessary for reaching the equilibrium to optimize the process. The removal of CECs from the mixture was assessed over 24 hours. The results are presented in Figures 1 and 2.

The process on both of the biosorbents is very fast. The adsorption is slightly faster when lignin is used, but also slightly faster adsorption in the first 30 min of most pharmaceuticals rather than pesticides and insecticides is notable. The equilibrium on lignin was reached after 90 min, while for RCs it took 180 min for most of the compounds. Faster adsorption on lignin could be due to smaller particle size (less than 224 µm) compared to RCs (224-400 µm) and thus greater total specific surface of lignin. Figure 1 indicates the greater adsorption capacity of RCs for pharmaceutical compounds rather than pesticides and herbicides.

Figure 1. Adsorption time-dependence of (a) pharmaceutical compounds and (b) pesticides and insecticides onto lignin and RCs

Removal of 14 out of 35 compounds was less than 20% after 24 hours by both investigated materials, so it was adopted that biosorbents showed a negligible affinity for their binding. The removal efficiencies for the rest of the components are shown in Figure 2. Raspberry canes showed somewhat better efficiency for most of the CECs. Maximum removal difference between lignin and raspberry canes was obtained for ofloxacin and malathion, 28% and 34%, respectively. For bezafibrate, carbamazepine, furosemide, and losartan (from the group of pharmaceutical compounds) as well as insecticide carbaryl and pesticides ethoprophos and methidation RCs showed removal less than 20% while lignin removed all these components with the efficiency of at least 40%.

Ligin of various origins and raspberry canes were also reported as potential biosorbents for the removal of Cr(VI) ions from aqueous solutions (Kukić et al., 2022; Lourenco et al., 2022).

Figure 2. Removal efficiency of CECs by lignin and raspberry cane after contact time of 24h

Fitting of kinetic data by different models provides more information about the process rate and rate-controlling step, which can be essential for setting up an adsorber. The results of fitting kinetic data of CECs adsorption onto lignin and RCs (data not presented) show extremely high values of correlation coefficient (R^2) for the pseudo-second-order model for both adsorbents (> 0.99) indicating that the limiting factor of the adsorption of CECs could be chemisorption since the pseudo-first-order model provided a comparatively poorer fit (< 0.93).

Conclusions

The adsorption process of CECs on both of the investigated biosorbents is very fast. The equilibrium on lignin was reached after 90 min, while for raspberry cane it took 180 min for most of the compounds. Faster adsorption on lignin could be due to smaller particle sizes compared to raspberry canes. Raspberry canes showed a greater adsorption capacity for pharmaceutical compounds rather than pesticides and herbicides and also somewhat better efficiency for most of the CECs. For bezafibrate, carbamazepine, furosemide, and losartan from the group of pharmaceutical compounds as well as insecticide carbaryl and pesticides ethoprophos and methidation raspberry canes showed removal of less than 20% while lignin removed all these components with the efficiency of at least 40%. The results of fitting experimental data by kinetic models showed extremely high values of correlation coefficient (R^2) for the pseudo-second-order model for both adsorbents indicating that the limiting factor of the adsorption of CECs could be chemisorption.

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References

- Alexa, E.T., Bernal-Romero del Hombre Bueno, M.d.I.Á., González, R., Sánchez, A.V., García, H., Prats, D. (2022). Occurrence and Removal of Priority Substances and Contaminants of Emerging Concern at the WWTP of Benidorm (Spain). *Water*, 14, 4129.
- Arous, F., Hamdi, C., Bessadok, S., Jaouani, A. (2019). Innovative Biological Approaches for Contaminants of Emerging Concern Removal from Wastewater: A Mini-Review. *Advances in Biotechnology & Microbiology*, 13(5), 114.
- González-González, R.B., Flores-Contreras, E.A., Parra-Saldívar, R., Iqbal, H.M.N. (2022). Bio-removal of emerging pollutants by advanced bioremediation techniques, *Environmental Research*, 214(2), 113936.
- Ho, Y.S., Wase, D.A.J., Forster, C.F. (1995). Batch nickel removal from aqueous solution by sphagnum moss peat. *Water Resource*, 29,1327–1332.
- Kukić, D., Ivanovska, A., Vasić, V. Lađarević J., Kostić M., Šćiban M. (2022). The overlooked potential of raspberry canes: from waste to an efficient low-cost biosorbent for Cr(VI) ions. *Biomass Conversion and Biorefinery*, 14, 4605-4619.
- Lourenço, A., Kukić, D., Vasić, V., Costa, R:A:, Antov, M., Šćiban, M., Gominho, J. (2022). Valorisation of Lignocellulosic Wastes, the Case Study of Eucalypt Stumps Lignin as Bioadsorbent for the Removal of Cr(VI). *Molecules*, 27(19), 6246.
- Lukić, D., Vasić, V., Živančev, J., Antić, I., Buljovčić, M., Đurišić-Mladenović, N., Šćiban, M. (2023). Preliminarna ispitivanja primene poljoprivrednog otpada kao biosorbenta za uklanjanje emergentnih zagađujućih supstanci iz vode, 9. Simpozijum Hemija i Zaštita Životne sredine ENVIROCHEM2023, 4.-7. Jun 2023. Kladovo Srbija, 65-66.
- Ofomaja, A.E. (2010). Intraparticle diffusion process for lead(II) biosorption onto mansonia wood sawdust. *Bioresource Technology*, 101, 5868–5876.
- Rakić, D., Antić, I., Živančev, J., Buljovčić, M., Šereš, Z., Đurišić-Mladenović, N. (2023). Solid-phase extraction as promising sample preparation method for compound of emerging concerns analysis. *Analecta Technica Szegedinensia*, 17(4), 16-24.
- Rout, P.R., Zhang, T.C., Bhunia, P., Surampalli, R.Y. (2021). Treatment technologies for emerging contaminants in wastewater treatment plants: A review. *Science of The Total Environment*, 753, 141990.
- Vasić, V., Kukić, D., Šćiban, M., Đurišić-Mladenović, N., Velić, N., Pajin, B., ... & Šereš, Z. (2023a). Lignocellulose-Based Biosorbents for the Removal of Contaminants of Emerging Concern (CECs) from Water: A Review. *Water*, 15(10), 1853.

Vasić, V., Lukić, D., Antić, I., Živančev, J., Ščiban, M., Đurišić-Mladenović, N., Rakić, D., Lourenco, A., Gominho J. (2023b). Adsorpcioni potencijal lignina izolovanog iz stabljike maline za uklanjanje emergentnih zagađujućih supstanci iz vode, 9. Simpozijum Hemija i Zaštita Životne sredine ENVIROCHEM2023, 4.-7. Jun 2023. Kladovo Srbija, 59-60.

NANO-GEOPOLYMER BASED REMEDIATION TECHNIQUES FOR PURIFICATION OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF GROUNDWATER WITH HIGH Mn, Fe AND OTHER METAL/METALLOID (As) CONTENT

Nenad Grba

*University of Novi Sad, Department of Chemistry, Biochemistry and Environmental Protection, Faculty of Sciences, Trg Dositeja Obradovica 3, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia,
nenad.grba@dh.uns.ac.rs*

Abstract

The primary objective of this research was to develop and implement innovative, sustainable, and cost-effective water remediation techniques, spanning from laboratory to pilot scale, utilizing novel nano-geopolymers without harming biota through irradiation. Groundwater contaminated with high manganese concentrations (ranging from 50 to 300 µg/l) was targeted for remediation using a newly developed purification process and a flow-through column system loaded with eco-friendly, low-cost geopolymers derived from natural Ecuadorian allophane (NatAllo).

Assessment of heavy metal removal efficiency, binding capacity, and leachability was conducted by using state-of-the-art mineralogical, thermo-analytical, spectroscopic methods, and mass spectrometry, aligning with local and EU guidelines. Groundwater from Novi Sad, Republic of Serbia, and Laktaši, Bosnia and Herzegovina, with elevated manganese levels, was successfully remediated to meet Maximum Allowable Concentration (MAC) values (below 50 µg/L), as per regulatory standards.

Experiments, both daily and multi-day, consistently demonstrated achievements below MAC values, corroborating initial batch results. Comprehensive instrumental analyses conducted by the Graz University of Technology, Austria, including Electron energy-loss spectroscopy (EELS), Transmission electron microscopy (TEM), and hydrochemical modeling through PHREEQ-C, provided valuable insights for optimizing batch and column performance, particularly for manganese and iron removal.

Post-column testing involved the characterization of nano-geopolymer materials using TEM and Powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD) analysis, focusing on Ecuadorian allophane. These findings underscore a significant scientific and practical breakthrough in water purification technology, paving the way for further advancements and applications in environmental remediation.

Keywords: Novel, Geo-polymer, Water-remediation, Techniques

Introduction

During the batch and column tests natural Ecuadorian allophane (NatAllo) showed the best cost-efficiency characteristics in an attempt to resolve dominantly Mn removal mechanisms to obtain the highest purification efficiency among their counterparts by chemo dynamics adsorption characteristics of Calcium silicate hydrates (C-S-H), montmorillonite (natural clay from Germany) and zeolite (natural sample from India) (Baldermann et al, 2018). The removal efficiency, binding capacity and leachability of heavy metals from groundwater was

assessed by thermo-analytical and spectroscopic methods and mass spectrometry, in line with national, local and EU guidelines.

The groundwater from Novi Sad (NS), Republic of Serbia has Mn content of 300 µg/L and 120 µg/L after aeration, sedimentation and filtration (A/S/F) and differently, groundwater from The Laktaši municipality (LM), Bosnia and Herzegovina, show a high geogenic Mn level that was not reduced even after A/S/F processes (Stojanović, 2017). After A/S/F treatment the LM results showed, a similar concentration of Mn in water as it was in the inlet groundwater (ca. 300 µg/l Mn) (please see Grba et al, 2022). However, for safe water operation and use, the contents of Mn have to be kept below the maximum acceptable concentration values (MACs) (<50 µg/l Mn). The daily and multi-day experiments conducted herein showed that Mn levels below MACs values were achieved by novel water purification system as followed: 1) continuous up-flow column system; 2) fluidized bed of dispersed allophane particles in water and 3) application of allophane particles on the nanoscale.

Similarly to the preliminary results obtained from the batch experiments, this was the first great scientific and applicable breakthrough and additional analyses were done. Based on the research conducted, this process enables the reduction of manganese concentration in represented groundwater samples by around 90% for NS water, and around 70% for LM ground, or A/S/F water (due to the geogenic origin of manganese). Therefore, the quality of the treated water defined by the Hygiene Safety of Drinking Water in the Republic of Serbia (Official Gazette of SR (42/98, 44/99 and 28/2019), Official Gazette of the Republic of Srpska (no. 40/03) and EU Directive 1998/83/EC was achieved.

Materials and methods

High-resolution (lattice fringe) Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) combined with Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) and Energy-dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) analysis, as well as Powder X-ray diffraction (P-XRD) analysis of water column-treated NatAllo and PHRASE-C-based hydro-chemical modeling of the collected water inlet and outlet solutions after successful column testings, removal of Mn at 90% from NS water, were used to trace and assess the processes underlying Mn removal from contaminated groundwater.

Results and discussion

The characterization was presented, with focus on analysing the structure of the highest/optimal performing material for water purification. NatAllo showed the best performance after groundwater treatment (50 up to 300 µg/l Mn) by a column (upflow, through the water system) system loaded with green and low-cost NatAllo. Subsequently, the hydrochemical modelling of unreacted and reacted solutions with PHREEQ-C software was used to further investigate the Mn removal process and to obtain charge balances, speciation, saturation states of relevant mineral phases of Mn-(hydr) oxides.

The sample NatAllo contains high amounts (~80 %) of the short-range-ordered clay mineral allophane, besides minor quantities (each <5 wt.%) of quartz, cristobalite, feldspar (albite and orthoclase), hornblende, halloysite, gibbsite, and goethite (Baldermann et al, 2018). The main lattice vibration bands of NatAllo, as indicated by infrared spectroscopy, are located between 1000–980 cm⁻¹ and at 870 cm⁻¹ due to Si–O–(Si) or Si–O–(Al) vibrations and Si–OH groups. The individual particles from NatAllo are ~5 nm in the largest dimension. The aspect ratio is equal to ~1. Such allophanes are often described as ring-shaped, hollow spherules or

allophane nano-balls. TEM-EDX analysis of NatAllo yielded an averaged atomic Al/Si ratio of ~ 1.3 , which is typical of so-called “stream deposit allophanes” or “silica spring allophane”. Minor amounts of Fe in NatAllo belong to fine-grained goethite, which is dispersed at the allophane surface. The specific surface area is $\sim 294 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$ for NatAllo, which is in the typical range of N_2 -BET values previously reported for natural allophanes ($\sim 200\text{--}400 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$) (Baldermann et al, 2018). It was note that the TEM analyses of the reacted NatAllo (i.e., after the column experiments) are currently in progress. However, XRD results indicate that Mn removal by NatAllo is a combination of (ad)sorption onto the allophane surface and chemical precipitation of Fe-Mn-(hydr)oxides.

As it is presented in Figure 1, the Mn content is extremely low at the allophane surface, which indicates that true surface adsorption is weak. However, neoformed particles with a rose-like shape that are not present in the original Nat-allophane sample were found. These particles contain Mn and have a d-value of $\sim 7.2\text{--}7.3 \text{ \AA}$, which is typical of the Mn-containing mineral birnessite.

Figure 1. Transmission electron microscopy (TEM) images of NatAllo after successful column tests showing allophane nano-ball structures and co-precipitated birnessite with rosette-like structures. The FFT patterns are used for birnessite identification

Independent evidence for birnessite formation comes from XRD data of the reacted allophane, where birnessite was identified in minor to trace amounts (depending on the ratio of Mn concentration in the inlet solution to the allophane load in the column). It is also notable that birnessite was supersaturated in the row (inlet) solution, as indicated by a saturation index (SI) of birnessite of 21.5, i.e., highly supersaturated. This all implies that the initially dissolved Mn ions (with oxidation state 2^+) precipitated dominantly as solid Mn-(hydr)oxide (i.e., birnessite, with oxidation state 4^+) upon water treatment, and that Mn sorption by allophane represents a subordinate process. The removal capacity for Mn by

natural allophane is very high, as indicated by reduction degrees for Mn in groundwater samples by up to ~90%.

This indicates that additional column tests as well as testing over longer time periods are recommended in order to find the best adsorption isotherm models and related highest adsorption capacity. This process enables the reduction of Mn concentration in groundwater samples by 90%, and therefore, the quality of treated water, as defined by the prescribe values, has been achieved (<50 µg/L).

The hydrochemical modelling of different water samples (i.e., raw, inlet and outlet solutions) with PHREEQ-C to obtain charge balances, speciation and saturation states of relevant mineral phases (i.e. Fe-Mn-(hydr)oxides) corroborates the XRD results (Table 1 and 2) and suggests further that Fe removal from the solution is due to chemical precipitation, while Mn removal is a combination of co-precipitation with Fe(oxy)hydrates and (ad)sorption onto the allophane.

Due to commercial use on the national level, Zeolite (clinoptilolite) from the Republic of Serbia shows a high adsorption capacity for heavy metals and metalloids e.g. arsenic and cost-efficiency characteristics (see also Grba et al, 2023).

Table 1. Input data for raw groundwater from Novi Sad, Serbia, inlet groundwater and treated groundwater after column (up-flow, through the water system) test

Sample parameters	Units	ROW WATER	INLET NS WATER	OUTLET NS WATER
T	°C	22.3	22.3	22.4
pH	-	7.0	8.5	8.7
SpC	µS/cm	n.a.	1255	1151
Ca	mg/l	188.8	73.3	53.7
Mg	mg/l	123.0	107.4	97.9
Na	mg/l	95.0	94.9	101
K	mg/l	7.0	6.9	6.9
Fe	mg/l	7.7	1.6	0.2
Mn	mg/l	0.30	0.10	0.01
Cl	mg/l	84.0	84.0	87.4
SO ₄	mg/l	565	451	218
HCO ₃	mg/l	706.4	400.2	319.0
IBE	%	n.a.	-4.01	10.95
NO ₃	mg/l	0.0	0.0	37.2
IBE	%	0.0	-4.01	0.0

Note: SpC - Specific Conductivity and IBE - Ion Balance Error (samples were within ±5%, which meets the testing accuracy requirements and reliability)

Table 2. Mineral characterization of natural Ecuadorian (NatAllo) allophane after groundwater remediation at high Mn concentration (from 50 to 300 µg/l) by a column (up-flow, through the water system) system

Minerals and related substances		Mineral parameters			Minerals and related substances		Mineral parameters		
Anhydrite	CaSO ₄	-1.1	-1.5	-1.9	Hematite	Fe ₂ O ₃	15.9	17.0	15.1
Aragonite	CaCO ₃	0.1	1.0	1.0	K-Jarosite	KFe ₃ (SO ₄) ₂ (OH) ₆	6.4	3.4	-0.5
Birnessite	MnO ₂	-13.3	-7.7	-7.9	Lepidocrocite	FeOOH	5.9	6.5	5.6
Bixbyite	Mn ₂ O ₃	-11.9	-3.7	-4.4	Maghemite	Fe ₂ O ₃	8.2	9.3	7.5
Calcite	CaCO ₃	0.3	1.2	1.2	Magnetite	Fe ₃ O ₄	20.4	20.5	17.6
Dolomite	CaMg(CO ₃) ₂	0.7	3.0	3.0	Manganite	MnOOH	-6.1	-2.0	-2.3
Fe(OH) ₂	Fe(OH) ₂	-4.2	-5.1	-6.2	Melanterit	FeSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	-5.0	-9.1	-10.8
Fe(OH) _{2.7} Cl ₃	Fe(OH) _{2.7} Cl ₃	7.4	7.6	6.6	Mn ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	Mn ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	-56.9	-57.9	-60.6
Fe ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	Fe ₂ (SO ₄) ₃	-31.9	-40.0	-43.9	MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	-13.8	-14.2	-15.2
Fe ₃ (OH) ₈	Fe ₃ (OH) ₈	3.8	4.0	1.0	MnSO ₄	MnSO ₄	-11.1	-11.5	-12.7
Ferrihydrite	Fe(OH) ₃	4.0	4.6	3.7	Nsutite	MnO ₂	-12.7	-7.1	-7.3
Goethite	FeOOH	6.8	7.3	6.4	Pyrochroite	Mn(OH) ₂	-7.0	-4.4	-5.0
Gypsum	CaSO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	-0.8	-1.3	-1.6	Pyrolusite	MnO ₂	-11.4	-5.8	-6.0
H-Jarosite	Fe ₃ (SO ₄) ₂ (OH) ₆	0.4	-4.1	-8.2	Rhodochrosite	MnCO ₃	-0.6	0.3	-0.5
Halite	NaCl	-6.8	-6.7	-6.7	Siderite	FeCO ₃	0.2	-2.5	-3.9
Hausmannite	Mn ₃ O ₄	-14.7	-3.9	-5.2					

Note: Negative values for mineral parameters are regarding the coordinates

Conclusions

Natural allophane (NatAllo) shows the highest efficiency for Mn removal from contaminated groundwater among all natural and synthetic geo-polymers tested in this research. This excellent performance in (waste) water processing and conditioning contributes to the unique structural properties of allophane, i.e., the high specific surface area, presence of surface functional groups and permanent vs. variable charges, which make allophane a good sorbent. Testing the nature of the Mn-Fe removal mechanism via FTIR, XRD, TEM and hydro-chemical modelling indicates that several Fe(oxy)hydrates are supersaturated with respect to the experimental solution, but distinct Mn(oxy)hydrates, as well as their chloride and sulphate forms, are generally not.

In summary, iron removal from groundwater is likely attributed to the chemical precipitation of iron(oxy)hydrates, whereas manganese removal involves a combination of co-precipitation with iron(oxy)hydrates and (ad)sorption onto natural allophane.

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References

Baldermann, A., Griebbacher, A. C., Baldermann, C., Purgstaller, B., Letofsky-Papst, I., Kaufhold, S., & Dietzel, M. (2018). Removal of Barium, Cobalt, Strontium, and Zinc from Solution by Natural and Synthetic Allophane Adsorbents. *Geosciences*, 8(9), Article 309. <https://doi.org/10.3390/geosciences8090309>

Council Directive 98/83/EC on the quality of water intended for human consumption.

Grba N., Baldermann, A. and Dietzel, M. (2023). Novel green technology for wastewater treatment: Geo-material/geopolymer applications for heavy metal removal from aquatic media, *International Journal of Sediment Research*, 38 (1), 33-48, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijsrc.2022.08.002>.

Grba, N., Kragulj-Isakovski, M., Stojanović, M., Šćiban, M., Tenodi, S., Dietzel, M., Baldermann, A., Krčmar, D., Savić M. and B. Dalmacija (2022). Priority substances in the groundwater of the Neogene Middle Posavina region and proposal for nano-geopolymer-based remediation techniques. *Int. J. Environ. Sci. Technol.* **19**, 3871–3888.

Hygiene Safety of Drinking Water in Republic of Serbia, Official Gazette of SR (no. 42/98, 44/99 and 28/2019).

Rulebook on hygienic safety of drinking water, Official Gazette of the Republic Srpska (no. 40/03).

Stojanovic M. (2017). Identification of external pressures and impacts on the groundwater quality of the sources in themunicipality of Laktaši, Doctoral dissertation.

LESSONS LEARNT FROM LIFE CYCLE ASSESSMENT OF ADVANCED WASTEWATER TREATMENT PROCESSES

Ferenc E. Kiss

*Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, University of Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia,
fkiss@uns.ac.rs*

Abstract

This study offers a comprehensive review of prior life cycle assessment (LCA) investigations focusing on various advanced wastewater treatment processes deployed for the elimination of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from urban wastewaters with the aim of establishing a technology ranking based on their environmental performance. Direct comparison proves challenging due to diverse functional units, system boundaries, impact assessment methods, and local conditions assumed in LCAs. Nevertheless, insights from previous LCAs suggest that adsorption with granular activated carbon exhibits a lower overall environmental impact compared to ozonation, while nanofiltration appears superior to reverse osmosis. These processes effectively reduce CECs in effluent and mitigate toxicity impacts; yet, significant trade-offs emerge on a life cycle basis. Indeed, the benefits from the reduced toxicity of the effluents are often offset by indirect toxicity at a regional/global level resulting from the adoption of resource-intensive wastewater treatment processes.

Keywords: Advanced wastewater treatment, Life cycle assessment, Environmental impacts.

Introduction

Wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) play a pivotal role in minimizing environmental pollution by effectively treating wastewater and mitigating the release of contaminants into the environment. Despite their crucial function, WWTP operations inherently carry an environmental footprint, stemming from resource and energy consumption, as well as the discharge of pollutants. This holds true for advanced wastewater treatment (AWWT) processes as well, which often entail significant demands in terms of chemical usage, energy consumption, and may give rise to harmful intermediates and residual byproducts (such as metal ion-containing sludge or exhausted solid catalysts).

In this context, life cycle assessment (LCA) emerges as a valuable tool for comprehensively analyzing the environmental impact of WWTPs. By adopting a life cycle approach – from resource extraction to final disposal – LCA ensures the thorough examination of all stages and their subsequent environmental implications. Consequently, this methodology identifies environmental hotspots and potential trade-offs across various categories of environmental concern. To shed light on the environmental rationale behind advanced wastewater treatment technologies like ozonation, activated carbon adsorption, membrane filtration, Fenton-reaction based, and solar and UV-based treatments, aimed at reducing the ecotoxicity potential of priority substances (PSs) and contaminants of emerging concern (CECs), this study presents a thorough review of past LCAs.

The primary objective of this research is to identify the strengths and weaknesses of specific advanced wastewater treatment processes utilized for the removal of PSs and CECs from urban wastewater treatment plants' effluents concerning their environmental impacts, facilitating a comparative analysis and offering insights into the most sustainable processes for future scaling-up.

Materials and methods

The SCOPUS database was utilized in February 2024 to select literature for review, with a specific focus on LCA studies of advanced wastewater treatment technologies applied for the removal of CECs and PSs. The search was restricted to advanced technologies delineated in Rizzo et al. (2019), which act as supplementary treatments for the removal of micropollutants (MPs) from urban wastewater treatment plant (UWWTP) effluents. Papers discussing the treatment of effluents from sources other than UWWTPs, such as industries and hospitals, were excluded from this study due to their distinctive compositions compared to typical UWWTP effluents. The selection procedure follows and extends upon the methodology described in Pesqueira et al. (2020), adhering to the same selection criteria.

Results and discussion

LCA studies addressing the environmental impacts of advanced treatments aimed at removing PSs and CECs from UWWTP effluents remain scarce. Only 31 papers were identified that fully met the selection criteria outlined in the methodology section. Among the most extensively researched systems are ozonation (OZ), photolysis under ultraviolet radiation (UV), and processes based on the Fenton reaction, while emerging treatments like heterogeneous photocatalysis are garnering attention. Additionally, conventional methods such as activated carbon (powdered – PAC or granular – GAC) adsorption and membrane filtration (nanofiltration – NF or reverse osmosis - RO) have also been thoroughly investigated. Generally, LCA results are specific to the goals and scopes of individual studies, shaped by their local contexts, making direct comparisons across different studies difficult, or in some cases even impossible (Pesqueira et al., 2020). Nevertheless, some comparative LCA studies evaluating various AWWT processes under similar conditions furnish valuable insights for ranking technologies based on their environmental performance. Based on their review of previous LCA studies Pesqueira et al. (2020) concluded that activated carbon typically exhibits comparable, albeit usually lower, environmental impacts than ozonation and lower impacts than reverse osmosis and UV-based processes (with or without H₂O₂ dosage) across most impact categories. However, it tends to underperform compared to nanofiltration. The primary advantage of activated carbon over ozonation is its lower energy consumption. This advantage is further accentuated if its regeneration is assumed, given that regenerating activated carbon requires less energy and resources than producing fresh adsorbents. Li et al. (2019) discovered that granular activated carbon performed worse than OZ and RO in toxicity-related impact categories due to its low micropollutant removal efficiency.

Among the AWWT technologies reviewed in Pesqueira et al. (2020), nanofiltration was found to be one of the most environmentally friendly options. In contrast to nanofiltration, reverse osmosis, another member of membrane technology, results in considerable environmental impact due to its substantial energy requirements. Rahman et al. (2018) compared reverse osmosis, UV + H₂O₂, ozonation and granular activated carbon and found that reverse osmosis has the highest impacts. The same was found by Li et al. (2019), who identified RO as the least favorable option for most analyzed impact categories when comparing toxicity-related impacts of ozonation, granular activated carbon, and reverse osmosis.

Ozonation is one of the most assessed technologies by studies focused on PSs and CECs. Based on their review of previous LCA studies, Pesqueira et al. (2020) concluded that ozonation is a more environmentally sound solution than reverse osmosis and UV, but less

so than nanofiltration, while exhibiting similar impacts to activated carbon. More recent studies also indicate that ozonation has comparable environmental impacts to GAC (Igos et al., 2021, Tarpani & Azapagic, 2023), but lower impacts than solar photo-Fenton (SPF) and higher impact than NF (Tarpani and Azapagic, 2023). Risch et al. (2022) determined that ozonation might have lower impacts than GAC in some toxicity-related impact categories, contingent upon whether ozone is produced with pure oxygen or air, with the latter being the preferable choice from an environmental perspective. The intensive electricity usage in the ozonation process is the primary driver behind its environmental impact, with results being highly sensitive to the assumed composition of the electricity mix (Andersson & Karlsson, 2022).

The environmental impact of Fenton reaction-based processes has been extensively investigated. When compared to other AWWT processes such as NF, GAC, and OZ, Tarpani and Azapagic (2023) identified the solar photo-Fenton (SPF) treatment as the least sustainable option. Pesqueira et al. (2021) determined that SPF has higher environmental impact than solar photolysis and solar photocatalysis using TiO_2 (with and without H_2O_2). In contrast, Foteinis et al. (2018) have found that SPF with H_2O_2 has the lowest environmental impact among the investigated light-driven processes (solar photolysis, photolysis under UV-A and UV-C irradiation with or without H_2O_2) but the results are very sensitive to the assumed electricity mix. There is significant variation between the environmental impact of different types of Fenton-based processes. In general, solar photo-Fenton is considered to be more sustainable than photo-Fenton with artificial/simulated light, as the solar process require less external energy (Pesqueira et al., 2020). At acidic pHs, photo-Fenton has lower environmental impact than electro-Fenton and photo-electro Fenton, however, the opposite is true at circumneutral pH (Conde et al., 2023). In most studies, energy and chemical use were identified as the two primary contributors to the overall environmental impacts of the Fenton-based processes. Coupling the solar photo-Fenton process with nanofiltration (Gallego-Schmid and Tarpani, 2019) or sunlight/ H_2O_2 (Maniakova et al., 2023) may reduce the overall impact of the process.

Comparing the environmental impact of UV-based treatment (UV + H_2O_2) to other AWWTs such as OZ, RO and GAC, Rahman et al. (2018) concluded that the UV-based process was the second worst option with only RO having higher environmental impact. Without the use of oxidants or catalysts, the UV-C process is approximately three times less harmful than the UV-A process, as it is significantly more efficient in removing micropollutants (Foteinis et al., 2018). If H_2O_2 is added, the environmental impact of the UV-process can be significantly reduced, regardless the fact that more chemicals are used in the process (Foteinis et al., 2018). Pesqueira et al. (2022) investigated the environmental justification of using sulphate-based oxidants such as peroxymonosulfate (PMS) and persulfate (PS) instead of H_2O_2 in UV-based processes and concluded that H_2O_2 is the best option environmentally based on both avoided and generated impacts. For UV-C treatments using H_2O_2 , electricity is the main hotspot, whereas for those applying PMS or PS, the applied chemical production is more relevant (Pesqueira et al., 2022). The use of nanostructures TiO_2 immobilized on a stainless steel mesh reduced the environmental impact of the UV-C process but not as much as the addition of H_2O_2 (Notarnicola et al., 2023).

Most comparative LCAs discuss the environmental impact of the analyzed process relative to other advanced wastewater treatment technologies. Studies that estimate the environmental justification for upgrading existing WWTPs with AWWT are still scarce. As expected, these studies determined an increase in the environmental impact of the upgraded WWTP in all non-toxicity-related impact categories (e.g., global warming, acidification, fossil depletion) due to indirect emissions and resource use in the life cycle of energy and material inputs of

the AWWT process. Surprisingly, they also revealed an increase in toxicity-related impacts (Rahman et al., 2018; Risch et al., 2022). This means that toxicity caused at a regional and global level caused by indirect emissions from upstream production of inputs to the AWWT outweighs the reduced local toxicity achieved from the reduction of MPs in effluents. This is mainly due to significant material and energy inputs associated with AWWT but also because of the relatively small number of MPs in the effluent considered in these studies. Furthermore, as shown by Pesqueira et al. (2022) characterization factors for many MPs found in wastewater effluents are still missing from life cycle impact assessment (LCIA) methods, therefore they tend to underestimate the achieved toxicity reduction associated with advanced treatment processes.

Conclusions

Based on the findings of the reviewed paper, it appears that adsorption using activated carbon offers a more favorable environmental perspective compared to ozonation, while the latter surpasses reverse osmosis. Nanofiltration also shows considerable promise. However, it's important to note that in adsorption-based and membrane processes, pollutants are not mineralized and require further treatment, a factor overlooked in previous LCAs. Similarly, potential toxic transformation products of ozonation and the potential impact of contaminated sludge generated in some advanced wastewater treatment processes were not accounted for in prior LCAs. A more comprehensive LCA has the potential to alter our understanding and ranking of different technologies. The LCA results for various advanced tertiary treatment processes for CEC removal highlight numerous environmental trade-offs when assessed on a life cycle basis. The local water quality improvements achieved through micropollutant reduction in effluents are often overshadowed by indirect environmental impacts at a regional or global level resulting from the production chain of materials and energy used in the process. The reviewed LCAs underestimate the benefits of AWWT due to the limited number of micropollutants considered in the studies and the absence of characterization factors for many CECs in currently available LCIA methods.

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References

- Andersson, S., & Karlsson, M. (2022). *A comparative life cycle assessment of advanced processes for the removal of pharmaceutical residues in wastewater*. 145. www.chalmers.se
- Conde, J. J., Abelleira, S., Estévez, S., González-Rodríguez, J., Feijoo, G., & Moreira, M. T. (2023). Improving the sustainability of heterogeneous Fenton-based methods for micropollutant abatement by electrochemical coupling. *J. Environ. Manage.*, 332.

Foteinis, S., Borthwick, A. G. L., Frontistis, Z., Mantzavinos, D., & Chatzisyneon, E. (2018). Environmental sustainability of light-driven processes for wastewater treatment applications. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 182, 8–15.

Gallego-Schmid, A., & Tarpani, R. R. Z. (2019). Life cycle assessment of wastewater treatment in developing countries: A review. *Water Res.*, 153, 63–79.

Igos, E., Mailler, R., Guillosoy, R., Rocher, V., & Gasperi, J. (2021). Life cycle assessment of powder and micro-grain activated carbon in a fluidized bed to remove micropollutants from wastewater and their comparison with ozonation. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 287, 125067.

Li, Y., Zhang, S., Zhang, W., Xiong, W., Ye, Q., Hou, X., Wang, C., & Wang, P. (2019). Life cycle assessment of advanced wastewater treatment processes: Involving 126 pharmaceuticals and personal care products in life cycle inventory. *J. Environ. Manage.*, 238, 442–450.

Maniakova, G., Polo López, M. I., Oller, I., Malato, S., & Rizzo, L. (2023). Ozonation Vs sequential solar driven processes as simultaneous tertiary and quaternary treatments of urban wastewater: A life cycle assessment comparison. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 413, 137507.

Notarnicola, B., Tassielli, G., Renzulli, P. A., Di Capua, R., Astuto, F., Mascolo, G., Murgolo, S., De Ceglie, C., Curri, M. L., Comparelli, R., & Dell'Edera, M. (2023). Life Cycle Assessment of UV-C based treatment systems for the removal of compounds of emerging concern from urban wastewater. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 857, 159309.

Pesqueira, J. F. J. R., Marugán, J., Pereira, M. F. R., & Silva, A. M. T. (2022). Selecting the most environmentally friendly oxidant for UVC degradation of micropollutants in urban wastewater by assessing life cycle impacts: Hydrogen peroxide, peroxymonosulfate or persulfate? *Sci. Total Environ.*, 808, 152050.

Pesqueira, J. F. J. R., Pereira, M. F. R., & Silva, A. M. T. (2020). Environmental impact assessment of advanced urban wastewater treatment technologies for the removal of priority substances and contaminants of emerging concern: A review. *J. Clean. Prod.*, 261, 121078.

Pesqueira, J. F. J. R., Pereira, M. F. R., & Silva, A. M. T. (2021). A life cycle assessment of solar-based treatments (H₂O₂, TiO₂ photocatalysis, circumneutral photo-Fenton) for the removal of organic micropollutants. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 761, 143258.

Rahman, S. M., Eckelman, M. J., Onnis-Hayden, A., & Gu, A. Z. (2018). Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of Advanced Wastewater Treatment Processes for Removal of Chemicals of Emerging Concern. *Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 52(19), 11346–11358.

Risch, E., Jaumaux, L., Maesele, C., & Choubert, J. M. (2022). Comparative Life Cycle Assessment of two advanced treatment steps for wastewater micropollutants: How to determine whole-system environmental benefits? *Sci. Total Environ.*, 805, 150300.

Rizzo, L., Malato, S., Antakyali, D., Beretsou, V. G., Đolić, M. B., Gernjak, W., Heath, E., Ivancev-Tumbas, I., Karaolia, P., Lado Ribeiro, A. R., Mascolo, G., McArdeall, C. S., Schaar, H., Silva, A. M. T., & Fatta-Kassinos, D. (2019). Consolidated vs new advanced treatment methods for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern from urban wastewater. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 655, 986–1008.

Tarpani, R. R. Z., & Azapagic, A. (2023). Life cycle sustainability assessment of advanced

treatment techniques for urban wastewater reuse and sewage sludge resource recovery. *Sci. Total Environ.*, 869, 161771.

ROLE OF A HIGH-RESOLUTION MASS SPECTROMETRY IN INVESTIGATING PROCESSES FOR REMOVAL OF CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN FROM WATER

Igor Antić*, Jelena Živančev, Maja Buljovčić, Dušan Rakić, Nataša Đurišić-Mladenović
University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, Bulevar cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia,
*antic@tf.uns.ac.rs

Abstract

Estimating human exposure to an environmental “cocktail” of chemicals is becoming one of the biggest challenges in modern science. The first and highest obstacle on that path is a reliable determination of as many as possible contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) present in environmental resources in trace amounts. Besides numerous chemicals discharged to the environment in parent forms, there are additional plethora of their transformation products (TPs) formed during various biotic and abiotic changes, including physical, chemical, and biological processes that have been investigated recently for removal of CECs from wastewaters. The CECs transformations may lead to even more polar and mobile environmental contaminants than their precursors and sometimes with increased toxicity; these TPs are also considered as CECs. In the last decade, a new horizon has opened with the development of powerful instrumental techniques based on high-resolution accurate-mass spectrometry (HRMS) and data processing software. The availability of many acquisition modes together with high mass accuracy and resolution of HRMS instruments enable wide-scope suspect screening (SSA) and non-target screening (NTS) of thousands of compounds. These new approaches request use of specialized software tools for data processing, which at the same time enable retrospective analysis of archived HRMS data sets, and, in this way, identification of CECs that have not been in focus during the first data processing. This work highlights the importance of HRMS in investigating CECs and their TPs in water, which is especially valuable for studies of the CECs removal processes.

Keywords: compounds of emerging concerns, transformation products, HRMS, suspect screening.

Introduction

More than two billion people worldwide need more safe and clean water according to UN World Water Development Report (United Nations, Climate action). To fulfill this requirement dozens of actions at the national and global levels need to be conducted including measurement of micropollutant concentrations in environmental mediums. Contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) include a vast group of chemicals with unknown or suspected toxic effects that are currently not regulated, controlled, or routinely monitored in the (aquatic) environment. CECs' ubiquitous occurrence attracts worldwide concerns due to potential risks they possess to the water environment and human safety (Antić et al., 2020).

Wastewater treatment (WWT) plants are one of the most important sources of CECs emissions in the environment i.e. pharmaceuticals, personal care products, pesticides, industrial chemicals, their metabolites, and transformation products (Petrović et al., 2014; Vasić et al., 2023). Namely, conventional WWT plants are not inherently designed to remove such micro-pollutants. Some authors (Sun et al., 2016) reported even negative removal rates of CECs during the water treatment. The presence of CECs in WWT plant effluents has been widely reported. Consequently, advanced treatment processes i.e., physical (adsorption, membrane filtration), chemical (ozonation and other advanced oxidation processes (AOPs), including O₃/UV, UV/H₂O₂, Fenton and Fenton-like oxidation, etc.), and biological (application of pure or mixed microbial cultures) are constantly developing to make an effort in removing

of CECs from wastewater (Kathi and Mahmoud, 2024). During the advanced WWT processes unexpected toxic transformation products (TPs), also considered as CECs, appeared (Wang et al., 2020) mainly through oxidation, hydroxylation, hydrolysis, conjugation, etc. of the parent micropollutants (Bletsou et al., 2015). In some cases, the transformation of parent compounds leads to even more polar and mobile products than their precursor chemicals, sometimes with increased toxicity. In developing advanced treatment technology for CECs efficient removal, their detection and quantification become one of the primary goals. It is of paramount importance to have robust analytical methodologies to investigate the presence of a wide range of CECs in untreated and treated wastewater to obtain a full scale of the water chemical status, related risks, and treatment efficiency. Additionally, the wide-range identification of CECs in environmental compartments is essential for regulatory purposes and for designing environmental remediation strategies (Sepman et al., 2023). The concentration range in which CECs are present requires highly selective and sensitive instrumentation (Bletsou et al., 2015). Most of the studies dealing with this issue are focused on target screening of limited number of pre-selected chemicals (Petrović et al., 2014; Skrbić et al., 2018, Antić et al., 2020).

In the last decade, suspect screening analysis (SSA) and non-target screening (NTS) have been increasingly used to detect the occurrence of numerous CECs in environmental matrices. Suspect screening analysis relies on lists of chemicals suspected to be present in the sample. Non-target screening is unrestricted of prior knowledge for the discovery of chemicals. Till now, most of the studies used SSA in comparison to true NTA (Manz et al., 2021). NTS for the CECs identification is challenging as a consequence of the absence of adequate high-resolution mass spectrometric information for the tentative and putative identification for numerous identified CECs. Nowadays, liquid chromatography coupled with HRMS is the technique of choice for investigation of CECs in environmental samples (Manz et al., 2023), particularly of water-soluble contaminants with polar functional groups that ionize under atmospheric pressure (Zhang et al., 2021) such as various pharmaceuticals and industrial chemicals.

Comparison of conventional target analysis with a new HRMS-based approaches in CECs determination

Target screening analysis, which typically focuses on a relatively small number of chemical species (from a few compounds up to several hundred using high-end instruments and the application of retention time-window-based SRM traces) is able to give only limited information on chemical status of environmental samples (Kaufman, 2012). The analysts have to strike a compromise between the number of transitions to be monitored, the length of the dwell times, and the number of data points across chromatographic peak of each compound from a pre-selected set of chemicals. In the target analysis, analytical standards of each studied CEC are necessary at the early beginning of method development. This includes time-consuming steps of previous individual compound-specific instrument tuning (e.g. obtaining selected reaction monitoring (SRM) information of each analyte of interest). The instruments used for target analysis are often unit mass low-resolution triple quadrupole mass analyzers (MS/MS) which cannot distinguish isobaric compounds, bringing false positive results.

Recent improvements in HRMS instruments enhance the sensitivity up to or even below the sensitivity of MS/MS, but at the same time HRMS instruments cover a larger number (e.g. several thousand) of analytes (Kaufman, 2012). This was achieved by technological advances in detection technology, the introduction of new ion transition devices, and the

higher resolution power, which reduces isobaric interferences with matrix compounds. For example, elemental compositions of ions up to 700 m/z could be elucidated by commercially available HRMS instrument based on Orbitrap technology (e.g. single-stage Orbitrap under the name Exactive of Thermo Fisher Scientific company, which technology was commercially available in 2008) operated at a mass resolution of 100,000 FWHM (full width at half maximum). Such resolutions permit the separation of ^{34}S isotopes (relative mass difference between the isotopic and the monoisotopic peak is 1.99580 u) from $^{13}\text{C}_2$ (relative mass difference between the isotopic and the monoisotopic peak is $1.00335 \text{ u} \times 2 = 2.0067 \text{ u}$) (Kaufmann, 2010). Full baseline separation of medium-mass ions can be observed when using a mass resolution of 100,000 FWHM (e.g. the Orbitrap Exactive). Recent innovations in HRMS mass analyzers, such as the development of the Compact High-Field Orbitrap mass analyzer and enhanced Fourier Transform (eFT) processing method, made it possible to achieve resolving powers as high as 1 million (Strupat et al., 2024). In particular, the ^{18}O peak (relative mass differences 2.00425 u) and the $^{33}\text{S}^{13}\text{C}$ (sum of relative mass differences $0.99939 \text{ u} + 1.00335 \text{ u} = 2.00274 \text{ u}$) peak can be separated at the baseline (1.5 mDa), while maintaining accurate isotopic abundances for all isotopes at the same nominal m/z value.

The second important parameter of each HRMS is mass accuracy and mass precision. Mass accuracy represents the ability of mass analyzer to determine the identity of the elemental composition of an ion signal based on m/z value determined from the mass spectrum. Accurate mass measurements in combination with high mass resolution enable fine depicting of molecule structure, which further reduces the list of possible elemental compositions. Taking into consideration accurate mass measurements, the compound can be matched with the database search (e.g. ChemSpider) (Arrebola-Liébanas et al., 2017).

Virtually all compounds present in a (prepared) sample extract can be detected simultaneously with powerful instruments developed in the last decade based on HRMS and data mining using open-source or commercial software (Figure 1). Still, it is important to emphasize that every step in a whole analytical procedure of sample manipulation, including sample preparation, reduces the "universe" of chemicals that enters the next analytical step as a consequence of interactions induced by physical and chemical properties of contaminants and analytical materials (such as solvents, solid phase used for extraction, LC stationary phases, ionization and HRMS conditions, etc.), so eventually there is no single instrument for "virtually all" compounds determination. The HRMS instruments are capable of simultaneously analyzing the sample in full scan and SRM mode. The compounds are identified based on mass accuracy data, retention time, isotopic patterns, MS/MS (or MSⁿ) fragments, etc. Not only developments in HRMS enabled full application of NTS but also developments in chromatography (liquid, LC, or gas, GC) as well as sample preparation methods.

Specificities of SSA and NTS

The application of LC-HRMS enables the identification of thousands of chemical features with specific mass spectra and retention time. During the HRMS analysis, massive quantities of data are generated. High-resolution mass spectrometric data need to be processed using open source or vendor's software options such as MZ mine, Envi Mass, Compound Discoverer, Bruker Metabolite tools, and Profile Analysis. Data processing of such data requires the usage of appropriate post-acquisition data-processing tools. Numerous data interrogation steps (blank subtraction, peak alignment, replicate analysis) can help in reducing the number of chemical features identified in one single run. After the application of

all pre-selected criteria for data reduction the number of peaks corresponding to non-targets can exceed 1000. In the next step of NTS analysis, the identified features are tentatively annotated by matching their tandem mass spectra (MS^2 or MS^n) with *in-silico* or experimental-determined mass spectra of a particular compound. For final confirmation, the analytical standard of the identified compound is needed (Bletsou et al., 2015).

Developments in open source or vendor's software enable generation of expected compounds nodes which consists of a list of m/z values for ionized parent compounds and their possible dealkylation, dearylation, and TPs. The application generates the list by using the structures of the parent compounds, the user-specified transformation lists (e.g. dehydration, hydration, methylation, oxidation, reduction, etc.) and number of combinatory steps, and the user-specified ionic species. This is of primary importance for the application during investigating processes for removal of CECs from water.

All the mentioned steps in chemical feature identification during the NTS analysis make this instrumental technique time-consuming and labor-intensive but bring to the identification of CECs presented in the investigated sample (Sepman et al., 2023). It is important to mention that HRMS data can be stored in some open access repositories and can be used as a "digital archive" of full scan HRMS and HRMS/MS spectra for further analysis if needed, for example, if new concerns or new knowledge on specific substances arise (Hollender et al., 2019).

Figure 1. Target and not-target workflow of HRMS analysis

Finally, the list of identified compounds, after the HRMS analysis and data processing, needs to be reported with a certain level of confidence. A harmonized protocol that defines the level of confidence with which a compound is identified is crucial. Currently, the generally accepted protocol for communication among users via the literature and databases relies on five identification levels, Figure 2 (Schymanski et al., 2014). Level 1 represents "certain identification" with a standard where MS^n matching and retention time were considered. Level 2 represents "probable identification" with an unambiguous match of the MS library spectrum (level 2A) and "probable identification" based on diagnostic evidence, but not confirmed by standard or literature information (level 2B). Level 3 represents the "tentative identification of a structure" where multiple structures are possible. Level 4 means

“unequivocal molecular formula”, certain molecular formula but no structure, and finally level 5 of confidence gives only a “measured exact mass of interest”.

Figure 2. Proposed confidence levels in CECs identification with HRMS

Conclusions

The number of potential CECs in environmental samples (i.e. WWT plant effluents) might be enormous, particularly keeping in mind the variety of TPs that can be formed during the advanced water treatments. The challenges of CECs identification and quantification during the HRMS NTS (including SSA) analysis are emphasized as thousands of chemical features with specific retention time and mass spectra can be detected. Processing of such data sets demands the latest software solutions, trained laboratory analysts for implementing various data interrogation steps (blank subtraction, replicate analysis, peak alignment), and tentative annotation of detected features with relevant HRMS databases, but it offers an extensive chemical profile of water samples, inevitable for further contaminants prioritization and risk assessment. Application of HRMS in CECs analysis elevates the levels of confidence of identified compounds taking into consideration not only molecular ion but also MSⁿ and library match. HRMS provides a robust capability for conducting semi-targeted or non-targeted screening, allowing analysts to not only detect potential peaks but also to identify and confirm the chemical structure underlying them.

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References

Antić, I., Škrbić, B.D., Matamoros, V., Bayona, J.M. (2020). Does the application of human waste as a fertilization material in agricultural production pose adverse effects on human health attributable to contaminants of emerging concern? *Environmental Research*, 182, 109132.

Arrebola-Liébanas, F.R., Romero-González, R., Frenich, A.G. (Eds.) (2017). *Applications in High Resolution Mass Spectrometry*. 1-14, Elsevier.

Bletsou, A.A., Jeon, J., Hollender, J., Archontaki, E., Thomaidis, N.S. (2015). Targeted and non-targeted liquid chromatography-mass spectrometric workflows for identification of transformation products of emerging pollutants in the aquatic environment. *Trends in Analytical Chemistry*, 66, 32–44.

Hollender, J., van Bavel, B., Dulio, V., Farnen, E., Furtmann, K., Koschorreck, J., & Tornero, V. (2019). High resolution mass spectrometry-based non-target screening can support regulatory environmental monitoring and chemicals management. *Environmental Sciences Europe*, 31, 42.

Kathi, S., Mahmoud, A.E.D. (2024). Trends in effective removal of emerging contaminants from wastewater: A comprehensive review. *Desalination and Water Treatment*, 317, 100258.

Kaufman, A. (2012). The current role of high-resolution mass spectrometry in food analysis. *Analytical and Bioanalytical Chemistry*, 403, 1233–1249.

Kaufmann, A. (2010). Strategy for the elucidation of elemental compositions of trace analytes based on a mass resolution of 100 000 full width at half maximum. *Rapid Communications in Mass Spectrometry*, 24, 2035–2045.

Manz, K.E., Feerick, A., Braun, J.M., Feng, Y.L., Hall, A., Koelmel, J., Manzano, C., Newton, S.R., Pennell, K.D., Place, B.J., Godri Pollitt, K.J., Prasse, C., Young, J.A. (2023). Non-targeted analysis (NTA) and suspect screening analysis (SSA): a review of examining the chemical exposome. *Journal of Exposure Science & Environmental Epidemiology*, 33, 524–536.

Petrović, M., Škrbić, B., Živančev, J., Ferrando-Climent, L., Barcelo, D. (2014). Determination of 81 pharmaceutical drugs by high performance liquid chromatography coupled to mass spectrometry with hybrid triple quadrupole–linear ion trap in different types of water in Serbia. *Science of the Total Environment*, 468-469, 415-428.

Schymanski, E.L., Jeon, J., Gulde, R., Fenner, K., Ruff, M., Singer, H.P., Hollender, J. (2014). Identifying small molecules via high resolution mass spectrometry: communicating confidence. *Environmental Science & Technology*, 48(4):2097–2098.

Sepman, H., Malm, L., Peets, P., & Kruve, A. (2023). Scientometric review: Concentration and toxicity assessment in environmental non-targeted LC/HRMS analysis. *Trends in Environmental Analytical Chemistry*, 40, e00217.

Škrbić, B.D., Kadokami, K., Antić, I. (2018). Survey on the micro-pollutants presence in surface water system of northern Serbia and environmental and health risk assessment, *Environmental Research*, 166, 130-140

Strupat, K., Scheibner, O., Bromirski, M. (2024). High-resolution, accurate-mass Orbitrap mass spectrometry –definitions, opportunities, and advantages. *Thermo Fisher Scientific*

(Bremen) GmbH, 28199 Bremen, Germany, TN64287-EN 12/16S, chrome-extension://efaidnbmnnnibpcajpcgclefindmkaj/https://assets.thermofisher.com/TFS-Assets/CMD/Technical-Notes/tn-64287-hram-orbitrap-ms-tn64287-en.pdf (accessed July, 2024).

Sun, Q., Li, M., Ma, C., Chen, X., Xie, X., & Yu, C.-P. (2016). Seasonal and spatial variations of PPCP occurrence, removal and mass loading in three wastewater treatment plants located in different urbanization areas in Xiamen. China. *Environmental Pollution*, 208, 371–381.

United Nations, Climate action, Water – at the center of the climate crisis, https://www.un.org/en/climatechange/science/climate-issues/water?gad_source=1&gclid=CjwKCAjwnK60BhA9EiwAmpHZw3vz8mDcPVuaCKLxgE87R5XDcJLX14tf1PBO4EF0YolmOsvsF8o5fBoCiaYQAvD_BwE (accessed July, 2024)

Vasić, V., Kukić, D., Šćiban, M., Đurišić-Mladenović, N., Velić, N., Pajin, B., Crespo, J.; Farre, M., Šereš, Z. (2023). Lignocellulose-based biosorbents for the removal of contaminants of emerging concern (CECs) from water: a review. *Water*, 15, 1853.

Wang, X., Yu, N., Yang, J., Jin, L., Guo, H., Shi, W., Zhang, X., Yang, L., Yu, H., & Wei, S. (2020). Suspect and non-target screening of pesticides and pharmaceuticals transformation products in wastewater using QTOF-MS. *Environment International*, 137, 105599.

Zhang, P., Carlsten, C., Chaleckis, R., Hanhineva, K., Huang, M., Isobe, T.,... & Wheelock, C.E. (2023). Defining the scope of exposome studies and research needs from a multidisciplinary perspective. *Environmental Science & Technology Letters*, 8, 839-852.

COMBINED ION EXCHANGE AND MICROFILTRATION

Marijana Dragosavac

Loughborough University, Ashby road, LE113JA, UK
m.dragosavac@lboro.ac.uk

Abstract

The purpose behind this work is to produce polystyrene-divinylbenzene cation exchange resin particles at various sizes, smaller than are conventionally available, and to use them in a microfiltration process; comparing the results with conventional column operation. In the seeded microfiltration process, surface microfilters with slots without internal tortuosity were used to minimize fouling. A filtration flux rate of $3432 \text{ l m}^{-2} \text{ h}^{-1}$ was achieved. Rates of copper sorption on to ion exchange resin were found to be dependent on mass transport limitations due to aqueous film diffusion and internal particle diffusion. For prediction of copper sorption a model that takes into account both film and internal diffusion was used. Microfiltration combined with ion exchange has the advantage of very fast kinetics, when compared to column use, and may provide better utilization of the resin particle, depending on the internal diffusion coefficient of the transferring species within the particle.

Keywords: Microfiltration, Slotted membranes, Ion exchange

Introduction

The research is focussed on heavy metal cations present in wastewaters from different industries including nuclear power plants, including: cesium (Cs^+), strontium (Sr^{2+}), and copper (Cu^{2+}). One of the methods for removing heavy metals from wastewaters is treatment in ion exchange columns. Columns with standard ion exchange resins have to fulfil the requirement that pressure drop within the column is low so the beads used in columns are usually large (greater than $200 \mu\text{m}$). There is a need that fine filtration, performed before the column, to ensure that material will not deposit on the particles. The easiest way to progress metal removal is to reduce the size of particles, but smaller particles lead to high pressure drops, which is not practical in column use.

As Holdich et. al. reported (2006), decreasing the ion exchange bead diameter increased the ion exchange utilization. They investigated boron removal from water during seeded microfiltration (a hybrid process which combines microfiltration together with ion exchange) and determined that at large particle sizes the resin was poorly utilized as only the layers close to the surface took significant concentrations of boron. At the small sizes the resin was better utilized, as the diffusion gradient within the resin bead was steeper and boron was more easily transported to the bead centre. They concluded that smaller bead sizes would increase the time before breakthrough and would provide better overall performance, but that small sizes may provide handling difficulties. So the beads should be neither too small, nor too large, and a size of $50 - 60 \mu\text{m}$ was reported as a good size.

Small beads may be produced by crushing conventional ion exchange beads, but crushing has two main problems:

- When crushed they have wide size distribution, and irregular shape,
- Because of the wide size distribution they will need to be separated into different fractions, this is time consuming and does not ensure optimal performance.

The project will make the ion exchange resin particles at the required sizes and use them in a microfiltration system. In such a system mass transfer is much faster and, once the transfer coefficients are deduced the modelling will compare the results with column use. Microfiltration combined with ion exchanger may have several potential applications, e.g.

adding ion exchange resin to a system containing activity in both water and solid phases it is possible to filter the water and suspended solids through the bed of resin resulting in a significantly decontaminated stream.

Materials and methods

For production of ion exchange beads membrane emulsification will be used, and for the preliminary tests sunflower oil was used to commission the system. Conventional ion exchange resin was used (Dowex 50WX8) for removal of copper ions as a test model in the initial seeded microfiltration work.

Figure 1. On the left equipment used for microfiltration. On the right Cumulative distribution curve for Dowex 50WX8 100-200

For the ion exchange studies, all reagents used were analytical grade chemicals. Solutions of copper ions with concentration between 1 and 100 ppm were made by dissolving appropriate amounts of $\text{Cu}(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (Sigma Aldrich, UK) in distilled water. The ion exchange resin was Dowex 50WX8 (strong acid cation resin containing 8% divinylbenzene) 100-200 obtained from Sigma Aldrich. The mean size and size distribution of Dowex 50WX8 100-200 was determined by laser diffraction particle size analyzer (LA-920, HORIBA). The mean size was 240 μm (Figure 1 on the right).

Analysis of copper was performed using an Atomic Absorbance Spectrophotometer (Spectra AA-200 Varian, UK). For microfiltration copper solutions with concentrations between 1 and 100 ppm were prepared. Mass of ion exchanger used was 0.1 or 1g. All microfiltration experiments were performed in the glass cell provided by Micropore Technology Ltd. UK, Figure 1 (on the left).

During all experiments a volume of 150ml was maintained in the cell. A slotted nickel membrane was fitted on the bottom of the glass cell. The membrane diameter was 3.2 cm and the working area was $8.4 \times 10^{-4} \text{ m}^2$. Fresh copper containing solution flowed into the cell (Influent) at the same rate as permeate was withdrawn from the cell (effluent). A peristaltic pump was used to induce the flow. At start-up, the cell was filled with distilled water and known mass of resin was added. A flow rate of 46 ml min^{-1} ($3432 \text{ lm}^{-2}\text{h}^{-1}$) was set. At

predetermined times 10 ml of effluent sample was collected and analyzed. If no ion exchange resin was used in the cell the system acts as a CSTR (continuous stirred tank reactor) and can be modelled as such.

Modelling

Combined IX and microfiltration

A mass balance for a well mixed system for copper can be expressed as below:

$$V \frac{dC}{dt} = F(C_o - C) - m \frac{d\bar{q}}{dt} \quad (1)$$

where V is the liquid volume in the cell, C is the concentration in the solution (both in the cell and the exit), C_o is the concentration in the feed to the cell, F is the feed flow rate, m is the mass of the resin in the cell and \bar{q} is the average mass of copper per mass of resin. The average mass of copper per mass of resin can be obtained by integrating the local mass throughout the resin form $r=0$ to $r=R$

$$\bar{q}(t) = \frac{3}{R^3} \int_0^R q(r,t) r^2 dr \quad (2)$$

where R is bead radius and the diffusion equation for mass transfer inside the particle is

$$\frac{\partial q}{\partial t} = \frac{1}{r^2} \frac{\partial}{\partial r} (D_{eff} r^2 \frac{\partial q}{\partial r}) \quad (3)$$

where r is radial position inside the particle and D_{eff} is effective diffusion coefficient of cation inside the particle. The mass rate of cation entering the particle is

$$m \frac{d\bar{q}}{dt} = kA(C - C^*) \quad (4)$$

where A is the surface area of the resin bead, C^* is the equilibrium concentration of cation at the surface of the resin and k is the mass transfer coefficient in the liquid phase. According to film theory

$$k = \frac{D_{liq}}{\delta} \quad (5)$$

where D_{liq} is the diffusion coefficient of cation in liquid phase and δ is the film thickness (distance over which the liquid phase diffusion takes place). Frossling equation is used to evaluate k , using Sherwood, Particle Reynolds and Schmidt dimensionless numbers

$$Sh = 2 + 0.6 Re_{slip}^{0.5} Sc^{0.33} \quad (6)$$

$$Sh = \frac{k \cdot 2R}{D_{liq}} \quad Sc = \frac{\mu}{D_{liq} \rho} \quad Re_{slip} = \frac{v_{slip} 2R \rho}{\mu}$$

where μ is the dynamic liquid viscosity and ρ is liquid density. Terminal velocity is depending on particle size and for small particles when Particle Reynolds number is smaller than 0.2, terminal velocity may be calculated by Stokes law:

$$v_{slip} = \frac{g(2R)^2(\rho_s - \rho)}{18\mu} \quad (7)$$

If Particle Reynolds number is larger than 0.2 various correlations can be used (Holdich 2002). For mass transfer coefficient combination of Frossling equation together with

Sherwood dimensionless number can be used. Rearranging the isotherm equilibrium concentration of cation at the surface of the particle can be expressed:

$$C^* = \frac{q|_{r=R}}{b(q_m - q|_{r=R})} \quad (8)$$

The cation exchange resin has a spherical shape, and using specific surface area of a sphere, surface area can be expressed as following:

$$\rho_s = \frac{m}{V_{resin}} = \frac{6m}{Ax} \Rightarrow A = \frac{6m}{\rho_s x} \quad (8)$$

V_{resin} is resin particle volume, ρ_s is density of the particle, A is surface area and x is diameter of the resin bead. Flux of the cation inside of the resin can be expressed as follows:

$$kA(C - C^*) = m \frac{dq}{dt} = A\rho_s D_{eff} \left. \frac{\partial q}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} \Rightarrow m \frac{dq}{dt} = \frac{3}{R} m D_{eff} \left. \frac{\partial q}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R}$$

So the mass balance of the cation is:

$$V \frac{dC}{dt} = F(C_o - C) - \frac{3}{R} m D_{eff} \left. \frac{\partial q}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} \quad (10)$$

For solving of differential equations boundary conditions have to be determined. At the start cell has fresh liquid:

$$q(t=0, 0 \leq r \leq R) = 0 \quad C(t=0) = 0$$

In the centre of the bead there is no cation at the centre ($r=0$).

$$\left. \frac{\partial q(t \geq 0)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=0} = 0 \quad (11)$$

And for the full radius of the bead ($r=R$) boundary condition is

$$\left. \frac{\partial q(t \geq 0)}{\partial r} \right|_{r=R} = \frac{k}{D_{eff} \rho_s} (C - C^*) \quad (12)$$

The system of equations must be solved simultaneously in an equation solver capable of solving partial differential equations, PDESOL (Numerica, Dallas, USA) was used. As a start, for model data the following were taken from Awang (2001).

Table 1. Data necessary for modelling of mass transfer during microfiltration with Dowex 50W8X 100 ion exchanger

q_m (mg mg ⁻¹)	b (m ³ g ⁻¹)	D_{liq} (m ² s ⁻¹)	D_{eff} (m ² s ⁻¹)
120.48	13.365	$7 \cdot 10^{-10}$	$7.2 \cdot 10^{-13}$

Results and discussion

Combined IX and microfiltration

Starting copper concentration in the feed solution was 1.2ppm when 0.1g of ion exchange resin was used and 1.5ppm when 1g of ion exchange resin was used. Experiments lasted for 5000 s. For both masses of resin the experiment was repeated and results are presented in Figure 4. As can be seen even after 5000 s, for both masses (0.1 and 1g), the resin was not saturated: an approximately. constant effluent concentration was reached which did not

correspond to the inlet concentration (C_0). Using the previously described model it was determined that it would take 2.5 days to reach the inlet concentration and a few characteristic parts on the modelled curves were deduced (Figure 2 **A**, **B** **C** and **D**).

Figure 2. Different mass of ion exchanger

From the Figure 2, it can be seen that the increase of copper concentration in the effluent is very quick at the start, and after that it reaches a constant value (**A-B**). In order to test the full capabilities of the resin the concentration of influent was increased to 100 ppm (Figure 3). It can be seen that the curve has the expected regions (**A**, **B** **C** and **D**). These are explained as follows. Region **A** indicates a quick increase in effluent concentration and is the period when the aqueous film concentration gradient develops, hence all the mass transfer resistance is in the aqueous film.

Figure 3. Different mass of ion exchanger

When a suitable concentration gradient is achieved and the resin has good internal diffusivity copper is easily transferred internally (region **B**). Internal transfer of copper will continue until resin resistance to mass transfer increases when copper concentration in the resin becomes high (region **C**), but at some point the resin will become saturated (region **D**).

Conclusions

As a model system for production of droplets sunflower oil was injected in to 2% Tween 20 solution and droplets in the size range between 184 and 50 μm were produced. Malik, et al. (2009) reported recently that it is possible to produce crosslinked polystyrene co-divinylbenzene adsorbent microspheres with median diameter between 40 and 300 μm in a similar device, and this will be used for future production of the ion exchange resin beads. In the seeded microfiltration process, surface microfilters with slots without tortuosity were used to minimize internal fouling. By using seeded microfiltration a high filtrate flux rate 3432 $\text{l m}^{-2} \text{h}^{-1}$ was achieved. Rates of copper sorption on to ion exchange resin were found to be dependent on mass transport limitations, due to aqueous film diffusion and internal diffusion and a model suitable for its analysis (and column prediction) was tested. Seeded microfiltration (microfiltration combined with ion exchange) may have several potential engineering applications, and may become a useful laboratory technique for transport property evaluation of resin particles and systems.

References

- Awang, A.R.B. (2001). Seeded microfiltration of copper with modified activated carbon, PhD Thesis, Loughborough University.
- Holdich R.G., cumming I.W., perni S. (2006). Boron mass transfer during seeded microfiltration. *Chemical Engineering Research and Design*, 84(1), pp. 60-68.
- Holdich, R.G. (2002). *Fundamentals of particle technology*. MidlandIT, Shepshed, UK.
- Malik, D., Webb, C., Holdich, R., Ramsden, J., Warwick, G., Roche, I., Williams, D., Trochimczuk, A., Dale, J. and Hoenich, N.,(2009). Synthesis and characterization of size-selective nanoporous polymeric adsorbents for blood purification. *Separation and Purification Technology*, 66, pp. 558-585.

POTENTIAL OF HYDROCHAR AS BIOSORBENT FOR HEAVY METAL IONS REMOVAL FROM WATER

Marco Barbanera^{1*}, Alessandro Cardarelli¹, Manuela Romagnoli², Vesna M. Vasić³, Dragana V. Lukić³

¹University of Tuscia, Department of Economics, Engineering, Society and Business Organization,
01100 Viterbo, Italy

² University of Tuscia, Department for Innovation in Biological, Agro-Food and Forest Systems (DIBAF),
01100 Viterbo, Italy

³University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad, bul. cara Lazara 1, 21000 Novi Sad, Serbia,
*m.barbanera@unitus.it

Abstract

Pollution of aquatic ecosystems with heavy metals, including drinking water resources and water intended for consumption, is one of the most critical issues worldwide. Over the last two decades, a wide range of treatment technologies have been investigated for the removal of heavy metals from water. Biosorption showed good performances in adsorbing these pollutants present in water at trace levels. Hydrochar has garnered significant attention as an adsorbent material, but further investigation is required into the alteration of material properties caused by the recirculation of process liquid. This is especially pertinent given that commercial hydrothermal carbonization (HTC) typically employs HTC process liquid recirculation to both preheat the feedstock and reduce wastewater accumulation. Therefore, this study aimed to investigate the impacts of process liquid recirculation up to 4 cycles, with a specific focus on the removal efficiency of Cr(VI) and Cu(II) ions from water throughout consecutive recycles. HTC of the exhausted chestnut from the tannin extraction industry was performed at a fixed temperature (270 °C), a fixed residence time (60 mins), and a solid/liquid mass ratio of 1/10. The adsorption studies were conducted in batch conditions. Obtained results showed good adsorption properties for the removal of Cr(VI) ions, while binding of Cu(II) ions was negligible. Kinetic studies showed that the experimental data fit with the pseudo-second-order model.

Keywords: Hydrochar, Hydrothermal carbonization, Heavy metals, Biosorption, Wastewater treatment

Introduction

The increased heavy metal contamination of water sources represents a growing concern for the population all over the world. Due to heavy metals' well-known toxic and carcinogenic nature, different studies have been conducted on their removal from water. The common methods include chemical precipitation, membrane filtration, ion exchange, adsorption on activated carbon, and reverse osmosis. Namely, these processes generate toxic sludge, consume large amounts of chemicals, involve high energy consumption, and are efficient and cost-effective only for heavy metal concentrations above 100 mg/l. Nowadays, the adsorption by biomass has received remarkable attention since it is efficient in adsorbing heavy metals present in effluents at trace levels. Focusing on biomass waste, its conversion into valuable products is particularly interesting. Hydrochar, formed through the hydrothermal carbonization of biomass in high-moisture environments, emerges as a promising material (Rodriguez-Narvaez et al., 2023). Agro-industrial residues, sewage sludge, and microalgae stand as typical sources for generating hydrochar, rendering it both cost-effective and environmentally sound (Zhao et al., 2023). In order to maximize the production of hydrochar, the reaction temperature is usually chose at around 180–280°C. Rich in hydrophilic functional groups, such as –COOH and –OH, hydrochar exhibits significant adsorption capabilities for heavy metal pollutants, making it a favored agent for water remediation purposes (Li et al., 2019). Variations in preparation parameters, including hydrothermal duration and

temperature, can significantly influence hydrochar characteristics like surface functional groups and specific surface area, thereby impacting its adsorption performance (Li et al., 2021). By tailoring the hydrothermal reaction conditions, it becomes possible to introduce diverse functional groups onto the hydrochar surface, thereby enhancing its affinity and selectivity towards different heavy metal contaminants.

Furthermore, HTC process also generates a substantial by-product known as process water (PW). PW carries away approximately 20–50% of biomass organics, leading to diminished hydrochar yield and contamination of the PW stream (Wang et al., 2019). If left untreated, PW poses potential environmental risks. However, conforming PW to emission standards inevitably escalates the HTC process's expenses, thereby diminishing its economic viability. Hence, there exists an urgent need to devise effective strategies that enhance hydrochar yield and performance while concurrently minimizing the costs associated with PW treatment, thus fostering the practical implementation of HTC technology (Ding et al., 2023). Within this context, the adoption of PW recirculation technology is emerging as an increasingly acknowledged solution for PW treatment. This technology holds the promise of diminishing PW treatment expenses and energy consumption while concurrently boosting hydrochar production (Picone et al., 2024). Under this frame, in the current study the effects of process liquid recirculation over four cycles on the hydrochar adsorption capacities of Cr(VI) and Cu(II) ions from water across successive recycles were examined. HTC tests of spent chestnut residue from the tannin extraction sector were conducted under constant conditions: temperature of 270°C, residence time of 1 hour, and solid-to-liquid mass ratio of 1:10.

Materials and methods

The exhausted chestnut wood leftover from tannin extraction was obtained from a tannin production facility in Radicofani (SI), Italy. Following collection, the material underwent drying at 105°C for more than 24 hours, followed by fine grinding and sieving to achieve a particle size smaller than 0.25 mm. For the HTC treatment, a stainless-steel Parr 4560 mini-batch reactor with a volume of 600 ml was utilized. In the initial HTC experiment, 30 g of exhausted chestnut wood was combined with 270 mL of deionized water (DW) and purged with nitrogen to eliminate air from the reactor. The reactor was then heated to the desired temperature (270°C) and maintained for 1 hour, with stirring set at 200 rpm. The solid and process water were separated using a Büchner funnel equipped with a vacuum pump and Whatman filter paper (8 µm). The resulting hydrochar was washed multiple times with distilled water and subsequently oven-dried at 105°C for 24 hours to eliminate residual moisture. Meanwhile, the process water obtained was utilized in the subsequent HTC experiment. Any reduction in water volume post-HTC (due to sample filtration, drying, or potential water consumption during the reaction) was compensated by adding DW until reaching 270 mL for the next run. In this investigation, four process water recycles were conducted at each reaction temperature. Hydrochars obtained after four cycles of process water recirculation (HY1, HY2, HY3, HY4), and the hydrochar obtained with distilled water (HY0) were used for the adsorption tests.

The preliminary adsorption studies of chromium and copper ions were conducted in batch conditions during 24h. Adsorption kinetic experiments were performed by mixing 0.1 g of hydrochar (HY0) with 100 mL of the chromium(VI) solution on a magnetic stirrer for 48 hours. At different time intervals (5, 10, 20, 30, 60, 90, 180, 360 min, and 24 and 48 h) the mixture was filtrated through a glass-fiber filter with a pore size of 0.45 µm. In the obtained filtrates the residual concentrations of chromium(VI) ions were analyzed by spectrophotometric

method (Rand et al., 1975). Experimental data were fitted using pseudo-first (Ofomaja, 2010) and pseudo-second-order kinetic models (Ho et al., 1995), and the Elovich model (Zeldowitch, 1939).

Results and discussion

Obtained results showed good adsorption properties for the removal of Cr(VI) ions, while binding of Cu(II) ions was negligible. Removal efficiencies of HY0, HY1, HY2, HY3, and HY4 were 40%, 20%, 26,5%, 27%, and 19%, respectively. Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that process liquid recirculation affects the adsorption properties of tested hydrochars, even if the number of recirculation steps does not have very significant impact. Hydrochar HY0 showed the best removal efficiency of Cr(VI) ions and was chosen for the kinetic studies. Time-dependence of chromium(VI) ions adsorption onto HY0 is shown in Figure 1. The process is rather slow, although it starts fast. In the first 5 min, 14% of the total amount of adsorbed ions are already bound to the surface, but after 6 h only 44 % of maximal adsorption capacity is reached. The equilibrium is reached after 24 h with the adsorption capacity of 29.4 mg/g.

Figure 1. Time-dependent adsorption of chromium(VI) ions onto HY0

Experimental data were fitted using three kinetic models: pseudo-first order and pseudo-second order models, and Elovich model. The results are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1. The value of the correlation coefficient (R^2) is the highest for pseudo-second order while the other two models showed much poorer fit. The calculated adsorption capacity corresponds to the experimentally obtained value (29.4 mg/g).

Table 1. Kinetic parameters obtained by different kinetic models for Cr(VI) ions adsorption onto HY0

Model	Equation	Ref.	Parameter	
Pseudo-first order	$\log(q_e - q_t) = \log q_e - \frac{k_1}{2.303} t$	Ofomaja, 2010	q_e (mg/g)	21.98
			k_1 (L/min)	0.00115
			R^2	0.6715
Pseudo-second order	$\frac{t}{q_t} = \frac{1}{k_2 \cdot q_e^2} + \left(\frac{1}{q_e}\right) \cdot t$	Ho et al., 1995	q_e (mg/g)	31.15
			k_2 (g/mg min)	0.0002
			R^2	0.9773
Elovich	$q_t = \beta \ln(\alpha\beta) + \alpha \ln t$	Zeldowitsch, 1934	α	71609.4
			β	0.2019
			R^2	0.8647

q_e and q_t (mg/g) are the amounts of chromium ions adsorbed per gram adsorbent at equilibrium and at time t (min); k_1 (L/min) is a pseudo-first-order rate constant, k_2 (g/mg min) is a pseudo-second order rate constant, α (mg/g min) is the initial rate of adsorption, β (g/mg) is desorption constant

The second-order model indicates the chemisorption of chromium ions on the surface of hydrochar and may be the step that determines the overall adsorption rate (Ho et al., 1995). Similar findings were reported by Kukić et al. (2019) and Lourenco et al. (2022) for the adsorption of chromium(VI) ions onto biochar from brewer's spent grain and lignin of different origins, respectively.

Conclusions

In this paper, promising outcomes have been achieved after examination of hydrochar as a biosorbent for the removal of Cr(VI) ions from water. Based on the obtained results, it can be concluded that process liquid recirculation decreases of about 50% the adsorption efficiency of the hydrochar but the number of recirculation steps does not have a significant impact. Kinetics of HY0 sample is well described by the pseudo-second-order model which indicates the chemisorption of chromium ions on the surface of hydrochar. Results obtained in this study indicate that examined hydrochar has a good potential for the removal of Cr(VI) ions from water, which is a step towards a circular economy approach in the field of solid waste management and the development of eco-friendly biosorbents.

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References

Ding, Y., Li, D., Lv, M., Yuan, L., Zhang, J., Qin, S., Wang, B., Cui, X., Guo, C. and Zhao, P., 2023. Influence of process water recirculation on hydrothermal carbonization of rice husk at different temperatures. *Journal of Environmental Chemical Engineering*, 11(2), p.109364.

Ho, Y.S., Wase, D.A.J., Forster, C.F. (1995). Batch nickel removal from aqueous solution by sphagnum moss peat. *Water Resource*, 29,1327–1332.

Kukić, D., Vasić, V., Radosavljević, M., Panić, S., Šćiban, M., Prodanović, J., Pejin, J.: Preliminarna ispitivanja međuproizvoda dobijanja aktivnog uglja iz pivskog tropa kao potencijalnog adsorbenta, VII Memorijalni naučni skup iz zaštite životne sredine „Docent dr Milena Dalmacija“, Novi Sad, 01.-02.04.2019., Zbornik radova (CD), V-02

Li, S.Y., Teng, H.J., Guo, J.Z., Wang, Y.X. and Li, B., 2021. Enhanced removal of Cr (VI) by nitrogen-doped hydrochar prepared from bamboo and ammonium chloride. *Bioresource Technology*, 342, p.126028.

Li, Y., Tsend, N., Li, T., Liu, H., Yang, R., Gai, X., Wang, H. and Shan, S., 2019. Microwave assisted hydrothermal preparation of rice straw hydrochars for adsorption of organics and heavy metals. *Bioresource technology*, 273, pp.136-143.

Lourenço, A., Kukić, D., Vasić, V., Costa, R.A., Antov, M., Šćiban, M., Gominho, J. (2022). Valorisation of Lignocellulosic Wastes, the Case Study of Eucalypt Stumps Lignin as Bioadsorbent for the Removal of Cr(VI). *Molecules*, 27(19), 6246.

Ofomaja, A.E. (2010). Intraparticle diffusion process for lead(II) biosorption onto mansonia wood sawdust. *Bioresource Technology*, 101, 5868–5876.

Picone, A., Volpe, M., Malik, W., Volpe, R. and Messineo, A., 2024. Role of reaction parameters in hydrothermal carbonization with process water recirculation: Hydrochar recovery enhancement and energy balance. *Biomass and Bioenergy*, 181, p.107061.

Rand, M. C., Greenberg, A. E. , Taras, M. J.: „Standard Methods: For the Examination of Water and Wastewater“, 14th Edition „American Public Health Association NW, Washington, DC, USA 1975.

Rodriguez-Narvaez, O.M., Nadarajah, K., Suarez-Toriello, V.A., Bandala, E.R. and Goonetilleke, A., 2023. Engineered hydrochar production methodologies, key factors influencing agriculture wastewater treatment, and life cycle analysis: A critical review. *Journal of Water Process Engineering*, 56, p.104483.

Wang, F., Wang, J., Gu, C., Han, Y., Zan, S. and Wu, S., 2019. Effects of process water recirculation on solid and liquid products from hydrothermal carbonization of *Laminaria*. *Bioresource technology*, 292, p.121996.

Zeldowitsch, J. (1934). Uber den mechanismus der katalytischen oxydation von CO and MnO₂. *Acta Physicochimica*, 1, 364–449.

Zhao, F., Tang, L., Jiang, H., Mao, Y., Song, W. and Chen, H., 2023. Prediction of heavy metals adsorption by hydrochars and identification of critical factors using machine learning algorithms. *Bioresource Technology*, 383, p.129223.

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About TwiNSol-CECs Project

TwINSol-CECs will generate the collaborative environment required for University of Novi Sad, Faculty of Technology Novi Sad (TFNS), Serbia, to increase and implement its research in the field of CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN (CECs). This will be accomplished by twinning under Horizon Europe programme with two EU research intensive institutions with strong expertise in the field:

- Spanish National Research Council, Institute of Environmental Assessment and Water Research (CSIC), Barcelona, Spain, and
- NOVA University Lisbon, NOVA School of Science and Technology (UNL), Lisbon, Portugal,

which eminent researchers will help TFNS to unlock the scientific potential through intensive networking, transfer of knowledge and technical expertise.

Surveillance of CECs and improvement of the removal technologies have important role in protection of humans and the environmental resources. Such efforts are in compliance with the European Green Deal (EGD) commitment for transition of EU to zero-pollution, toxic free environment. They are also in line with the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Preserving the quality of water, air, and soil, protecting the drinking water sources, and promotion of the water protection, and pollution reduction from the source to tap, are among the priority actions of EU Strategy for the Danube Region.

TFNS recognized the Twinning Western Balkans call under HORIZON EUROPE programme of European Union as an opportunity to reinforce own capacities already proven in innovative CECs analysis and removal methodologies and to strengthen its position in the European Research Area. The project answered the call requirements, and it was evaluated with 14.5 out of 15. It started on August 01, 2022 and will last 3 years. The project maximum grant is 1 432 937.50 Euros. The full project name is "TWINNING FOR ENHANCING THE SCIENTIFIC EXCELLENCE OF FACULTY OF TECHNOLOGY NOVI SAD FOR INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS TO PROTECT ENVIRONMENTAL RESOURCES FROM CONTAMINANTS OF EMERGING CONCERN".

The project represents a coherent set of knowledge, skills, experience, and awareness raising activities, dissemination, communication, networking, coordination, etc. for successful achieving of the project objectives.

More about the project with the latest news on project activities and events may be found at the project web site www.twinsol-cecs.com.